

HORIZON 2020

State of the Art of Health Research and Innovation (R&I) in EU regions

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Grant agreement number:	643574
Project acronym:	RegHealth-RI
Project title:	The European Regions Network for Health Research & Innovation.
Funding scheme:	Horizon 2020 – 2014 – single-stage
Due date of deliverable:	Project month 7
Actual submission date:	27 June 2016
Version:	Final Version
Dissemination level:	Public

UNIVERSITÀ
DEGLI STUDI DI TRIESTE

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Acknowledgements	Ziberna, Lovro
Suggested citation	Cozza C., Plechero M, Gómez-Núñez, Antonio J. and Guinea J. (2016). <i>State of the Art of Health Research and Innovation (R&I) in EU regions</i> . Deliverable 1.1 of project RegHealth-RI.
Executive summary (or abstract) of the report	<p>The report aims to provide a comprehensive overview of Health Research and Innovation (R&I) in European countries and regions. With the use of different well-established data sources (e.g. Eurostat and WHO), new data provided by the European Commission focusing on Health thematic priority, but also data on clinical trials and educational infrastructure elaborated for the first time at NUTS2 level by University of Trieste, the report analyzes through different statistical techniques the current status of Health R&I in EU regions. The report also analyses the possible causes and influencing factors of national and regional disparities in Health R&I, with a specific focus on less performing EU regions. The report provides an ‘operationalization’ of the framework developed jointly with project partners. It also includes a first attempt to build a composite indicator at country level for research excellence in Health. From the report it emerges that the divide between countries and regions is different in terms of publications output with respect to patenting output and that the country success in FP7, with few exceptions, seems to be quite in line with the country research performances. When analyzing the possible factors influencing Health R&I it results that R&D investment and human resources may have an important role in explaining different countries performances although some of these countries seem to use resources more efficiently than others. The report highlights also some problems related to the lack of specific and homogenous data on Health for all countries/regions as well as problems in the use of some specific indicators for Health such as the composite indicator for measuring research excellence.</p>
RegHealth-RI	<p>The European Regions Network for Health Research & Innovation (RegHealth-RI) is a 2-year project funded by the EU under the Horizon 2020 framework aimed at analysing, discussing and improving the performance of health research & innovation across the different EU regions.</p> <p>The final goal of the RegHealth-RI project is to contribute in a significant way to three key Horizon 2020 goals, namely, (i) reducing the gaps in health R&I across the EU regions, (ii) widening the participation in H2020 and (iii) facilitating synergies between H2020 and Structural Funds.</p>
RegHealth-RI partner organisations	<p>Sociedad para el Fomento de la Innovación Tecnológica (INNOVATEC), SPAIN. [<i>Coordinator</i>].</p> <p>European Regional and Local Health Authorities (EUREGHA), EUROPE.</p> <p>University of Trieste (UNITS), ITALY.</p>
Website	http://rhing-net.eu/reghealth-ri/

STATE OF THE ART OF HEALTH RESEARCH AND INNOVATION (R&I) IN EU REGIONS

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1. INTRODUCTION

1.1. Importance of health R&I in Europe

Health represents, today even more than in the past, a pivotal asset for the growth and cohesion of world society. This is particularly true for the EU: as stated by the OECD in the publication *Health at a Glance: Europe 2014*, “European countries have achieved significant gains in population health, but there remain large inequalities in health status both across and within countries”. The efforts made by EU governments are reflected in several recent indicators: Health represents the second most important budget line in EU countries; overall the 73% of Health expenditures is funded by the public sector; and one employee out of 10 works in this sector (EC, Investing in Health, 2013). Therefore, especially in an EU society where life expectancy constantly grows, investing in Health has to be considered a compulsory task for achieving economic prosperity and social cohesion.

Indeed, Health is no more intended as a simple value in itself. Investing in the efficiency of Health systems and especially on prevention will bring also increases in work productivity and a reduction in social inequalities. Such goals are strictly related to the capability of Health Research and Innovation (R&I) actors to make substantial advancements in the field. Not by chance, Health (together with Demographic change and Well-being) is one of the societal challenges of the EU Horizon 2020 programme. Health goals are, therefore, intrinsically contained in the EU R&I approach.

More in details, the Horizon 2020 addresses the inequalities in the field of Health, in order to find the right policy measures to reduce the gap among EU countries and regions. Such a gap might be particularly significant in the R&I domain, thus implying a minor efficiency of some national and/or regional Health systems. Following the approach mentioned above, less R&I in Health systems might lead to the worsening of the work and social conditions of some EU areas.

The key role of Health is also confirmed by the fact that it is one of the most recurrent priorities for EU regions’ smart specialization strategies (S3, see Sörvik and Kleibrink, 2015). Indeed regions in almost all EU countries claim Health as their S3 priority. However, different regions might refer to specific – and very different – sub-areas of Health, targeting it from very different perspectives. That is, for instance, referring to Health when dealing with the Pharmaceuticals, Biotech or Medical technology sectors, eventually key in their territory; or simply when dealing with their ageing population; or maybe meaning the introduction in their systems of healthcare innovations, such as e-Health.

Map 1 – Regions with Health within the set of EU priorities¹

This variety of meanings for the field of Health is not surprising. Until now, scholars have faced, without solving it, the difficulty in clearly defining the boundaries of the field of Health. For the purposes of the current report, a data-driven definition has been adopted. As it will be explained in the following sub-section (1.2) of this introduction chapter, our approach does not solve this problem, but allows comparing empirical evidence coming from very different secondary data sources. In other words, we believe it is still not possible to create an *ex ante* definition of what Health should be. It is rather wise to use as much information as possible and, while making data comparisons, highlighting the possible discrepancies in the definitions. To make an example, in *section 2* of this report there will be distinct sub-sections presenting alternatively the number of

¹ Source: EC, JRC, IPTS (2016). EYE@RIS3. *Smart Specialization Platform (S3)*. <http://s3platform.jrc.ec.europa.eu/map>. [Accessed: 16/06/2016].

Medical schools and Health publications. In these sub-sections, all relevant information will be presented in figures and tables. However, when in *sub-section 3.1* the two sets of variables will be correlated, it will be recalled how the analysis could be driven by figures coming from very different data sources.

The difficulty in measuring Health R&I in the EU is not only an issue of definitions. There are at least other two main constraints. On the one side, Health is a very peculiar field: it includes manufacturing (e.g. the pharmaceuticals) and services (e.g. the hospitals) activity; it includes very strong investment both by the public and by the private bodies; it affects both the macro level institutions (the entire society, the associations of large private organisations, etc.) and the very-micro ones (SMEs, professionals, individual citizens). The Health sector is really a mirror of the overall society. On the other side, then, there is a more practical problem that affects the current report (and the project behind it): it is the first time that a comprehensive mapping of R&I in Health across EU regions is attempted.

In fact, the joint analysis of R&I figures at the NUTS2 regional and sectorial (Health) level is not straightforward. Usually the deepening of one dimension (i.e. the regional one) excludes that of the other one (the sectorial). Also the most important publication on the innovativeness of EU regions (that is the Regional Innovation Scoreboard) does not fully cover any specific sector. Regional/sectorial analyses are usually included in case studies or in reports covering one country only or other limited breakdowns. To the best of our knowledge, no report has provided a comprehensive mapping of Health R&I in all NUTS2 regions of the EU-28. In this fact resides the novelty of the current report.

Such a novelty has implied a big effort in gathering and comparing data at the regional level. Effectively, beside the difficulty in the definition of Health, also the lack of available data with a sectorial and regional breakdown has represented an important constraint for analyses conducted so far (Charlesworth et al, 2009; Røttingen et al., 2013). As it will be shown throughout *sections 2 and 3*, this problem has been tackled with two main tools:

1. The development of a novel framework for analysing Health R&I;
2. The constant use of both national and regional level data, complementing each other when possible.

As regards the first point, the comprehensive overview of Health R&I in European countries and regions in this report has been developed starting from the building blocks of the RegHealth-RI framework, jointly developed by project partners (see fig.1 in *sub-section 1.3.1*). As it will be explained, the framework covers all possible concepts and actors in the R&I domain, from its funding (mostly starting from EU policies, that is FP7 and H2020) to its long term social and economic outcomes. Not all blocks of the framework will be touched in this report, but the aim of the framework is to show that Health R&I is a longitudinal topic that cannot be observed with a narrow-minded approach.

As regards the second point, although the report is focused on the *regional* level, some key indicators are presented at the *national* one, as no regional breakdown is possible. In addition, for several EU countries the NUTS2 regional and the national levels coincide: it is the case of countries with very different backgrounds and location, such as Luxembourg, the Baltic countries, Malta and Cyprus. Finally, the use of national data allows the breakdown and comparison between *Widening* and *non-Widening* EU countries (European Union, 2014).

Therefore, the joint analysis of the two levels has been adopted strategically, to make as many comparisons as possible. More in details, throughout *section 2* the building blocks of the RegHealth-RI framework will be analysed:

- First, providing a methodological explanation of the variables used in each block;
- Second, displaying the country-level empirical evidence;
- Third, showing the NUTS2 regional breakdown, whenever possible.

The focus of the section is therefore to describe and analyse national and regional disparities in terms of Health R&I.

Sub-section 3.1 detects the common patterns in key variables on Health R&I within EU regions. Again, a specific sub-section is devoted to the analysis of the situation of the less performing ones. The analysis is mostly relying on correlations among the most relevant indicators identified in the previous sections. *Sub-section 3.2* performs an in-depth regression analysis on the determinants of publishing propensity. Since scientific publications in Health have come out to be a relevant indicator for the scientific involvement of EU regions, this section tries to explain in details which are the explanatory variables more associated with the Health publishing propensity. *Sub-section 3.3* shows an attempt made within the RegHealth-RI project to develop a composite indicator for Research Excellence in the Health sector. Such an indicator replicates for the Health sector, with minor adjustments, the one developed by the European Commission – JRC (European Commission, 2012 and 2013).

The report ends with a useful section for national and regional policymakers. Then, *section 4* provides some conclusions and recommendations and discusses policy implications related to the analysis conducted. The section partially uses the outcomes of two project workshops (one held in Madrid, in June 2015, and another one held in Trieste, in November 2015).

1.2. The concept of *health*

Until now, the constraint in properly measuring R&I in such a complex sector as Health has been due to two factors: (i) the difficulty in clearly defining the boundaries of the sector and the (ii) lack of available data.

The first problem resides not only in the generic definition of Health that, as already mentioned in the introduction, represents a totally unique sector. The main difficulty is also understanding the “borders” of Health when dealing with the R&I scope.

In this report a pragmatic approach has been adopted. In fact, the data sources used in the analysis are very different in nature: business expenditures in R&D (BERD) are typically measured on the basis of the sector of economic activity of firms, thus Health can only be a kind of “sum” of its main sub-sectors (e.g. Pharmaceuticals and Medical devices ones); medical schools existing in EU universities are basically defined on the basis of the subjects (e.g. Medicine, Pharmacy) which are taught in them; data referring to the FP7 and Horizon 2020 (and also scientific publications and patents) are classified in terms of the Thematic priority of projects; and so on.

In other words, the high variety of meanings for the Health sector leads to an unsolved definition of its boundaries. We have acknowledged that it is still not possible, nor wise, to create an *ex ante* definition of what Health should be. Indeed, the definition of Health has been empirically driven by the availability of data: it is, in each set of data, the closest concept to the framework described above. So we use the sector of economic activity when dealing with private companies (as in the BERD example mentioned); but then we use the FP7 thematic priority when dealing with EU-funded projects. The aim has been to gather the highest possible number of data: an *ex ante* definition of Health would have limited the data gathering to almost nothing and made almost impossible to develop different typologies of comparisons.

However, we also acknowledge that a large debate on the *ex ante* definition of Health in relation to R&I has taken place over the last years. We recall hereafter the most relevant points of this debate.

In the OECD report related to R&D in Health (2001, page 9) it is stated that *‘in the widest sense we are interested in all R&D which is relevant to human health. Here there are no generally accepted international definitions or guidelines on coverage. “There are few (if any) areas of investigations which can “logically” be excluded from possible relevance to health – perhaps cosmology” (Wilk, 1996)’*. Such a comment confirms that Health R&I concerns a very high number of fields.

The same report affirms that the usual breakdown by field of science provided by the EUROSTAT in the compilation of GBAORD (Government budget appropriations or outlays for research and development) might be limited. These *“data are essentially political series and the classification of the funding of different programs and institutions depends on how the government presents its R&D priorities as well as on the formal mandates of the institutions concerned. For example, the whole of the National Institutes of Health is included in “health” in the United States, as is the Medical Research Council in the United Kingdom. In other countries, such as France, where there is a general research council, funds for very similar projects may be included in “advancement of research”. In countries, which leave the higher education sector to carry out the national long-term research effort, the same project might be included in “General University Funds” (OECD 2001, pag.20).*

Furthermore, the GBAORD broken down by socio-economic objective (SEO) as collected by OECD has only one specific health related category, *‘Health (excluding pollution)’*, which is defined as follows: *“This category covers R&D programs directed towards the protection and improvement of human health. It includes R&D on food hygiene and nutrition; radiation used for medical purposes, biochemical engineering; medical information; rationalization of treatment and pharmacology (including the testing of medicines and the breeding of laboratory animals for scientific purposes): as well as research relating to epidemiology, prevention of industrial diseases and drug addiction”*. We therefore end up ignoring the Health R&D as defined in GBAORD statistics. However, GBAORD data will be used in section 3.1, also to show to what extent they are limited (e.g. the importance of key countries as the Netherlands or Belgium, home of many Health Multinational Corporations, would be extremely reduced, according to these data).

Finally, we acknowledge the existence of a wide number of *technical* definitions of Health. It is the case of the Health Research Classification System². However, the creation of these technical definitions is not aimed at studying R&I from a socio-economic point of view (as in this report). Then, the use of these definitions would be misleading for our purposes.

²See: http://www.hrcsonline.net/sites/default/files/HRCS_Document.pdf

1.3. Methodology

1.3.1. The RegHealth-RI framework

As anticipated above, the RegHealth-RI project consortium has developed a comprehensive framework for the analysis of Health R&I across EU regions. The visualisation of the framework is provided in figure 1.

The framework includes three main blocks that can be considered the “core” of Health R&I, plus two sets of actors and indicators that help to explain the content of R&I dynamics. These three main blocks are:

1. R&I inputs in the Health sector;
2. The Actors and the Activities of Health R&I;
3. R&I outputs of the Health sector.

The two additional sets of indicators regard:

4. The End-users of Health R&I;
5. The External conditions, which coexist with and influence the Health R&I process.

A clear “starting point” for the Health R&I process cannot be identified, as the outputs of R&I – especially the long term ones – are also to be considered inputs for the development of the whole process itself. However, for descriptive purposes, we start from the block considering R&I investments. They mostly regard the decisions that policymakers and businessmen (especially officers of large companies) take for sustaining the R&I activities.

Indeed, this first block is strongly linked to the second one: the activities undertaken by public and private bodies involved in Health R&I rely on the amount of R&I investments set at the previous stage. These two aspects are not separated in practice, as the amount of R&I investments might depend on previous achievements of R&I actors. In fact, if an actor of the R&I process has managed to obtain good results from past activities, it is more likely that its governing body will devote even more resources (in monetary terms) to extend and improve these past results.

Figure 1 – The RegHealth-RI project framework

The second block of the framework regards the Actors and the Activities of Health R&I. This part of the framework is more articulated: it starts assuming that there are two main typologies active in the R&I process, that is public and private entities. Among the first typology, two sub-typologies exist: Universities³ and Public Research Organisations. However, given the peculiar nature of the Health sector, we also include here the sub-typology of Public Hospitals. Within the second typology (private entities), the sub-typologies are private firms and non-profit organisations.

In this second block, three other items are shown: the Research and the Innovation processes themselves, and the knowledge flows within the actors of these processes. As from a well-established literature, the Research and Innovation processes cannot be measured in themselves (Rosenberg, 1982 and 1994; Kline and Rosenberg, 1986). They are usually measured through their inputs or in their outputs and outcomes. However, it was meant here that the main story of Health R&I resides in the activities that are constantly undertaken within the single actors of this process. Differently, the knowledge flows among actors can be measured by means of specific indicators such as co-publication or co-patenting, which will be explained together with the rest of indicators in *section 2*.

The third main block of the framework concerns the results of the R&I process. This definition has been largely debated within the project consortium, as it included very different measures. In general, it is meant to include here all the possible results, which can be:

- Short-term results, such as the development of human resources and most typical outcomes of the R&I processes, such as knowledge creation via scientific publications and patents.
- Medium-term results, including more concrete outputs (such as new drugs, better diagnostics and treatments, etc.) and in general and enhanced Health systems.
- Long-term results, ranging from an improved population Health to socio-economic growth. These results will not be treated within this report, but it is worthy to bear them in mind of policy and decision makers working in the design and development of policy measures and activities aimed at having beneficial impacts on population of EU regions and countries.

To conclude with the description of the framework, it has to be recalled that many of the actors of Health R&I are end-users of other actors' efforts. In the part of the framework related specifically to end-users, we have included five typologies: the Higher education and Scientific communities, the Industry, the Health System and the overall Society. In parallel to the R&I results, these end-users are linked to specific parts of the framework. To understand the holistic approach of the framework, Industry can be the end-user of the research process of a public research centre; in the same time, Industry actors can provide new products and processes adopted by the Health system (e.g. in hospitals); this, in turn, can provide the improvement of societal Health, as well as an increase in Health jobs (eventually due to process innovations), leading to socio-economic growth.

The overall content of the framework is affected by the existence of External conditions. We refer here to local and global variables, which play a role in shaping the positive or negative dynamics of the Health R&I process. External conditions have to be intended as the contextual conditions and factors that may have an effect on the economic growth and innovation of the system. The OECD (2014) considers for example as framework conditions the labour, capital and product markets. Recent literature, when discussing regional R&I in relation to a specific sector, refers more explicitly to the institutions (formal and informal rules and regulations settled down also by public authorities) and the organizational structure of a region (density and quality of organizations) (Chaminade and Plechero, 2015; Tödtling et al. 2011; Tödtling and Trippl, 2005).

³ Although Universities can be also private, we include them in the first typology. We follow here the usual breakdown coming from the Frascati Manual (OECD, 2002) for R&D sectors of performance: private, public, higher education, non-profit organisations.

In relation to important external conditions, which involve the institutional aspects, we should consider the quality of the government and the different Policies that are in place at the regional level and that are related not only specifically to Health. In fact, the Health R&I process can be limited by the absence of specific policies, but also by the decision of Governments to put more efforts (and money) in other budget lines. Similarly, the existence of a long tradition of Health policies in some countries and or regions, and their cumulateness, might lead to a better situation than in another territory. In other words, the same Health policy adopted in two different contexts with a different background of past policies and effectiveness, might lead to very different outcomes.

Another crucial External condition is represented by the existence of R&I resources in both the public and the private sectors, outside the Health scope. That is, some infrastructures that are not necessarily related to Health might ease the Health R&I process. Having many Universities or Private Research Organisations in a country/region, even if not explicitly dealing with Health, might facilitate the work that Health schools in universities undertake (it might be the case of basic science departments as Physics, but also ICT departments).

Similarly, the existence of local business networks or of global scientific network – in which the Health R&I under observation is placed – might give rise to positive spillovers (Boschma and Iammarino, 2009; Feldman and Audretsch, 1999). In such a case, the Health R&I process of a country/region would be reinforced, in relation to another territory where such spillovers do not take place. More generically, the existence of a good potential market has a role in pulling R&I results. This potential market is of course global, nowadays, but it is worth reminding that for some peripheral EU regions the local and neighbourhood markets are still very relevant. Finally, another measure adopted in this report analysis is represented by the indexes for Quality of Government.

Furthermore, the regional industrial structure and regional specialization in Health with respect to other industries or the general related variety of the region should be considered (Frenken et al., 2007). This related variety deals with a crucial aspect: the industry composition of a regional economy and the degree of similarity that exists across sectors. For instance, one might argue that in regions where sectors that are complementary and reinforcing in terms of competences exist, R&I performances are superior.

The analysis of the External conditions is not treated in a specific section of this report but rather they underlie in all sections. In particular we refer to those dealing with quantitative analysis (correlations in *sub-section 3.1* and regressions in *sub-section 3.2*).

1.3.2. Variables and indicators

Table 1 below summarizes the most relevant variables that will be presented in the descriptive statistics of the *section 2* of this report, as well as in the analytical analysis conducted in *sub-sections 3.1* and *3.2*. In the column 1, we recall the block of the framework where the corresponding variables and specific indicators have been derived from. Both variables and indicators are then listed in the columns 2 and 3 of the table respectively. From columns 4 to 10, we have included the subject scope by delineating health (column 4), the level of analysis at country and/or region whether regional breakdown exists (column 5), the sector of performance (column 6), the unit of measure used for counting or expressing the indicator (column 7), the data sources used to compile the data (column 8), and the concrete dataset extracted for implementing each indicator (column 9).

Table 1 – List of principal indicators used in the report

Framework Block	Variable	Indicator	Subject scope	Level of analysis	Performing Sector	Measure	Data source	Data set
R&I INPUTS	<u>Expenditures</u>	I1 – R&D expenditure	Health	Country	All (total without breakdown)	% GDP	OECD / EUROSTAT	2010 or Latest available year
			Health (Pharmacy)	Country	Business enterprise	€ Million by Million population	EFPIA (R&D expenditure of pharmaceutical industry)	2013 2012 (Czech Republic, Denmark, France, Hungary) 2011 (Austria, Croatia, Netherlands)
	<u>Human Resources</u>	I2 – Total R&D personnel	Health (Medical and health sciences)	Country	Public sector and Higher Education	Full-time equivalent (FTE) by Million population	EUROSTAT	2011 (it is the year with the lowest number of missing values in the series)
		I3 - Researchers	Health (Medical and health sciences)	Country	Public sector and Higher Education	Full-time equivalent (FTE) by Million population	EUROSTAT	2011 (it is the year with the lowest number of missing values in the series)
R&I ACTORS AND ACTIVITIES	<u>Business Enterprise Sector</u>	I4 – Biotech companies	Health (Biotech)	(1) Country (2) Region	Business enterprise	Absolute figures	LABIOTECH	Data until 2016
		I5 – Health clusters	Health (Biotech, Health, Medical, Pharmaceutical)	(1) Country (2) Region	Business enterprise	Absolute figures	Cluster Observatory	Data until 2016
		I6 – Science parks	Health (Biotech, Health, Medical, Pharmaceutical)	(1) Country (2) Region	Business enterprise	Absolute figures	Cluster Observatory	Data until 2016

	Higher Education Institutions	I7 – Active Medical Schools	Health (Medicine)	(1) Country (2) Region	Higher Education	Absolute figures	IMED (FAIMER)	Data until 2015	
		I8 – Active Pharmacy schools	Health (Pharma)	(1) Country (2) Region	Higher Education	Absolute figures	FIP AIM	Data until 2015	
	Knowledge flows	I9 – Intra-country co-publications	Health	Country	All (total without breakdown)	Absolute figures by Million population	EC-DG-RTD Framework Contract	Average 2008-2012	
		I10 – International co-publications	Health	Country	All (total without breakdown)	Absolute figures by Million population	EC-DG-RTD Framework Contract	Average 2008-2012	
		I11 – Intra-country co-patenting	Health	(1) Country (2) Region	All (total without breakdown)	Absolute figures by Million population	EC-DG-RTD Framework Contract	Average 2008-2010	
		I12 – International co-patenting	Health	(1) Country (2) Region	All (total without breakdown)	Absolute figures by Million population	EC-DG-RTD Framework Contract	Average 2008-2010	
	R&I OUTPUTS	New R&I human resources	I13 – PhD students (ISCED level 6)	Health and welfare	Country	Higher Education	Absolute figures by Million population	EUROSTAT	Average 2008-2012
		New R&I infrastructures	I14 – Research infrastructures	Health (Biological and Medical Sciences)	(1) Country (2) Region	All (total without breakdown)	Absolute figures	MERIL	Data until 2016
		Knowledge creation	I15 – Peer-reviewed publications	Health	(1) Country (2) Region	All (total without breakdown)	Absolute figures by Million population	EC-DG-RTD Framework Contract	Average 2008-2012
I16 – Top publications			Health	Country	All (total without breakdown)	Absolute figures by Million population	EC-DG-RTD Framework Contract	Average 2008-2009	

		I17 – Patent applications	Health	(1) Country (2) Region	All (total without breakdown)	Absolute figures by Million population	EC-DG-RTD Framework Contract	Average 2008-2010
	<u>New products and processes</u>	I18 – On-going clinical trials	Health	(1) Country (2) Region	All (total without breakdown)	Absolute figures by Million Population	CENTERWATCH	Data until 2015
<u>PERFORMANCE IN EU RESEARCH FRAMEWORK PROGRAMMES</u>	<u>EU funded project participation</u>	I19 – Participation in FP7	Health	(1) Country (2) Region	All (total without breakdown)	Absolute figures by Million Population	CORDA (EC)	All FP7 period (2007–2013)
		I20 – Participation in H2020	Health	Country	All (total without breakdown)	Absolute figures by Million Population	CORDA (EC)	Data until 2015
<u>INNOVATION COMPONENT</u>	<u>Innovation performance</u>	I21N – Innovation Union Scoreboard	All	Country	-	Qualitative scale (innovation leaders, innovation followers, moderate innovators, modest innovators)	Innovation Union Scoreboard	Edition 2015
		I21R – Regional Innovation Scoreboard	All	Region	-	Qualitative scale (innovation leaders, innovation followers, moderate innovators, modest innovators)	Regional Innovation Scoreboard	Edition 2014
		I22 – Granted Patents	Health	Country	All (total without breakdown)	Absolute figures by Million Population	EC-DG-RTD Framework Contract	Average 2008-2010
		I23 – SME Instrument Applicants	Health	Country	All (total without breakdown)	Absolute figures by Million Population	CORDA (EC)	Data until 2015
		I24 – SME Instrument Success	Health	Country	All (total without breakdown)	Absolute figures by Million Population	CORDA (EC)	Data until 2015

Table 1 should already be meant as a project outcome in itself, mainly due to the following three reasons:

- The comprehensive mapping of Health R&I available data has allowed us to start filling in the most important gaps, with a novel data gathering. It has been, for instance, the case of Health University infrastructures, for which we regionalised the number of Medical, Pharmacy and Veterinary Schools existing at the moment in the EU-28; and that of on-going clinical trials, whose estimation made by the WHO was only at the national level, while with the RegHealth-RI project it has been regionalised, as well.
- The mapping also allows identifying other key variables that should be calculated for regional Health R&I, but whose complexity could not be faced by the limited resources of the RegHealth-RI project. We refer here to the measurement of regional Health brain drain as well as regional Health inward Foreign Direct Investment (FDI). These are just two examples, but a dedicated brainstorming on these informative gaps is surely needed, eventually at the EU, OECD or WHO level. The modest outcome of this project report is to suggest the most urgent ones.
- Finally, to complement the existing indicators used by the European Commission, the search for a composite indicator of Health R&I is perceived as useful. The ones calculated in *subsection 3.3*, in fact, are still country-level measures. Indeed, Health is more and more a regional issue, especially in the framework of the S3 or for the purposes of the synergies between Horizon 2020 and EU Structural Funds. To cope with these regional strategies, a regional indicator should be developed: to do that, a preliminary extension of regional Health R&I variables should be foreseen by EU countries and regions.

Definitions and delineations of all indicators calculated and included in this report are provided in table 2. The first three columns have already been presented in table 1 and refer to the framework block, variable and indicator respectively. In addition, table 2 also includes a last column aimed at providing comments and notes to explain the objective and scope of each, or in other words, what indicators mean and try to measure.

Table 2 – List of principal indicators used in the report

Framework Block	Variable	Indicator	Definition and Notes
R&I INPUTS	<u>Expenditures</u>	I1 – R&D expenditure	This indicator includes all monetary resources devoted to Research and Experimental Development, that “comprise creative work undertaken on a systematic basis in order to increase the stock of knowledge, including knowledge of man, culture and society, and the use of this stock of knowledge to devise new applications” (OECD, 2002). See: http://www.oecd.org/innovation/inno/researchanddevelopmentstatisticsrds.htm
	<u>Human Resources</u>	I2 – Total R&D personnel	This indicator includes “all persons employed directly on R&D, as well as those providing direct services such as R&D managers, administrators, and clerical staff” (OECD, 2002). See: http://www.oecd.org/innovation/inno/researchanddevelopmentstatisticsrds.htm
		I3 – Researchers	“Researchers are professionals engaged in the conception or creation of new knowledge, products, processes, methods and systems and also in the management of the projects concerned” (OECD, 2002). See: http://www.oecd.org/innovation/inno/researchanddevelopmentstatisticsrds.htm
R&I ACTORS AND ACTIVITIES	<u>Business Enterprise Sector</u>	I4 – Biotech companies	Biotechnology can be defined as “the application of science and technology to living organisms, as well as parts, products and models thereof, to alter living or non-living materials for the production of knowledge, goods and services (OECD (2001). See: https://stats.oecd.org/glossary/detail.asp?ID=219 The counting of biotechnology companies covered by this indicator relies on own criteria of portal “Labiotech.eu”.
		I5 – Health clusters	This indicator counts number of health clusters according to classification criteria of portal “European Cluster Observatory”, which includes: Biotech, Health, Medical and Pharmaceuticals fields. See: http://www.clusterobservatory.eu/index.html
		I6 – Science parks	Similarly to the previous indicator, health science parks are counted on the basis of classification criteria elaborated by the team of the European Cluster Observatory and including Biotech, Health, Medical and Pharmaceuticals fields. See: http://www.clusterobservatory.eu/index.html

	<u>Higher Education Institutions</u>	I7 – Active Medical Schools	This indicator refers to the number of active medical school based on coming from FAIMER, which is a non-profit foundation for advancement of international Medical education and research. The directory used for elaborating the data is the International Medical Education Directory (IMED: http://www.faimer.org/), which is a free web-based resource for accurate and up-to-date information about international medical schools that are recognized by the appropriate government agency in the countries where they are located. It is important to notice that a medical school is added to IMED after FAIMER receives confirmation from the Ministry of Health, Ministry of Education, or other appropriate agency that the Ministry or agency has recognized that school.
		I8 – Active Pharmacy schools	This indicator refers to the number of active pharmacy school according to the dataset coming from the Official World List of Pharmacy Schools: http://academic_institutional_membership.fip.org/world-list-of-pharmacy-schools/
	<u>Knowledge flows</u>	I9 – Intra-country co-publications	This indicator includes – from each country perspective – all scientific publications written together with authors from the same country.
		I10 – International co-publications	This indicator includes – from each country perspective – all scientific publications written together with authors from foreign countries.
		I11 – Intra-country co-patenting	This indicator includes – from each country perspective – all patent applications undertaken with inventors from the same country.
		I12 – International co-patenting	This indicator includes – from each country perspective – all patent applications undertaken with inventors from foreign countries.
<u>R&I OUTPUTS</u>	<u>New R&I human resources</u>	I13 – PhD students (ISCED level 6)	Counting of total PhD students in this indicator was done on the basis of the International Standard Classification of Education (ISCED 1997). Thus, level 6 “is reserved for tertiary programmes which lead to the award of an advanced research qualification”. A main criterion for the definition of this level is the requirement of “the submission of a thesis or dissertation of publishable quality, which is the product of original research and represents a significant contribution to knowledge”. Correspondence with the updated version of this classification (ISCED 2011) is the level 8, entitled as “Doctoral or equivalent level”. http://www.uis.unesco.org/Education/Documents/isced-2011-en.pdf

	<u>New R&I infrastructures</u>	I14 – Research infrastructures	The article 2 (6) of Regulation (EU) No 1291/2013 of 11 December 2013: <i>Establishing Horizon 2020 – the Framework Programme for Research and Innovation (2014-2020)</i> , defines research infrastructures as “facilities, resources and services that are used by the research communities to conduct research and foster innovation in their fields. They include: major scientific equipment (or sets of instruments), knowledge-based resources such as collections, archives and scientific data, e-infrastructures, such as data and computing systems and communication networks and any other tools that are essential to achieve excellence in research and innovation. They may be 'single-sited', 'virtual' and 'distributed'. On the one hand, delineation of health infrastructures was done by selecting the field of “Biological and Medical Sciences” in the database of infrastructures “MERIL”. On the other hand, ‘distributed infrastructures’ were counted based on different locations (as registered in MERIL database) excepting when they are placed in the same region/country.
	<u>Knowledge creation</u>	I15 – Peer-reviewed publications	This indicator includes all scientific publications published in each country/region.
		I16 – Top publications	This indicator includes the top 10% most cited scientific publications.
		I17 – Patent applications	“A patent is a right granted by a government to an inventor in exchange for the publication of the invention; it entitles the inventor to prevent any third party from using the invention in any way, for an agreed period”. Before being granted (see below), the requested patents are named “applications”. See: https://stats.oecd.org/glossary/detail.asp?ID=2023
	<u>New products and processes</u>	I18 – On-going clinical trials	On-going clinical trials are active recruiting studies done in clinical research. See: http://www.centerwatch.com/clinical-trials/
<u>PERFORMANCE IN EU RESEARCH FRAMEWORK PROGRAMMES</u>	<u>EU funded project participation</u>	I19 – Participation in FP7	This indicator refers to participation of regions or countries in topics related to health in FP7.
		I20 – Participation in H2020	This indicator refers to participation of regions or countries in topics related to Societal Challenge 1 “Health, Demographic Change and Wellbeing” of H2020.
<u>INNOVATION COMPONENT</u>	<u>Innovation performance</u>	I21N – Innovation Union Scoreboard	The Innovation Union Scoreboard “provides a comparative assessment of the research and innovation performance of the EU Member States and the relative strengths and weaknesses of their research and innovation systems. It helps Member States assess areas in which they need to concentrate their efforts in order to boost their innovation performance” (European Commission, 2015).

		I21R – Regional Innovation Scoreboard	The Regional Innovation Scoreboard (RIS) “is a regional extension of the Innovation Union Scoreboard” whose main goal is to address the lack of regional innovation data by providing statistical facts on EU regions’ innovation performance”. (European Commission, 2014a).
		I22 – Granted Patents	After being accorded the right on an invention, patent applications (see above) become granted patents.
		I23 – SME Instrument Applicants	This indicator refers to the number of applicants for projects of the SME Instrument of H2020. It includes all the proposals presented within the SME instrument.
		I24 – SME Instrument Success	This indicator covers the number of successful proposals, or in other words, proposals being funded, within the SME Instrument of H2020.

1.3.3. Data sources and datasets used

Over the last years, the Health R&I topic has been studied by scholars belonging to several international institutions. We refer here to reports and studies published by the European Commission (especially via the JRC), the OECD or the World Health Organisation. Many efforts have been made for measuring Health R&I. However, the level of analysis has always been set at the country-level. The regional breakdown of Health R&I has been ignored or, in few cases, limited to a small part of the analysis.

It is for instance the case of the Science Metrix report titled '*Cross-Cutting Analysis of Scientific Publications versus Other Science, Technology and Innovation Indicators*' (European Commission, 2013). Indeed, this report presents figures on national scientific and technological strengths also for the Health sector. Scientific strengths are measured by the number of scientific publications and technological strengths by patent applications at the European Patent Office (EPO). It also shows two maps of Health R&I outcomes at the NUTS2 regional level. In other words, the regionalisation of the same outcomes (publications and patents) is shown. However, no other analysis of this regional level is provided, nor additional regional variables on Health are discussed.

Therefore, this report aims at further developing the regional/sectorial (Health) breakdown, extending the analysis on scientific and technological strengths of EU regions to additional (and in some cases, novel) indicators. However, there exist few data on Health at regional level in specific sources of value for statistical analysis up to now. Most of these sources are constrained by particular issues, above all the lack of regional or sectorial break down of data collected. For this reason, several and heterogeneous sources were searched for and, consequently, different datasets were finally used. Principal data sources of potential interest for this report together with corresponding limitations are detailed in the following:

- EUROSTAT: The NUTS2 regional breakdown is frequent, but its intersection with the health sectorial level is not available.
- OECD.Stat: The NUTS2 regional breakdown is absent; furthermore, country-level data are provided only for OECD countries plus a limited set of additional countries, thus not covering the entire EU-28.
- WHO Global Observatory on Health R&D is still in early stage and NUTS2 regional breakdown is absent.
- On scientific publication databases such as Web of Science (Thomson Reuters) or Scopus (Elsevier), the two largest and more reputed collections of academic literature at present, many issues arise in relation to attribution of authorship (D'Angelo, Giuffrida and Abramo, 2010) or lack of data in affiliation of authors for counting and subsequent aggregation of publications at higher levels of analysis (Egghe, Rousseau and Van Hooydonk, 2000), etc.
- On other international data sources and reports (e.g. RICYT, PAHO or UNESCO), the Health focus regards even supranational areas, with no country level data.
- Patent databases like Espacenet from European Patent Office, also present a high complexity for defining health field and, above all, when delineating country production because of the many variables to be taken into consideration, i.e. country of the inventor, country of patent owner, etc. This is even worse when regional delineation has to be done.

All these data sources, however, provide useful insights for the analysis of Health R&I. In fact, the above mentioned institutions have launched several projects on the topic, although through country-level analysis. It is the case of the WHO that in 2013 organised an 'Informal workshop on monitoring financial flows in support of health research & development' (WHO, 2013). This workshop has reinforced, in particular, the idea of overcoming the limitations of data availability for Health R&D. Following the WHO workshop, the newly-born Global Observatory for Health R&D by OECD and WHO

has already started to work on better indicators for measuring Health R&D⁴. In this report, we have used some of those indicators such as the estimation of Health GERD and data on on-going clinical trials, both at the country-level. However, according to the Observatory itself, a lot of work still remains to be done in order to provide stakeholders with the best information to monitor and assess Health R&I in all countries and regions.

Regarding the data gathered for the statistical analysis conducted in this report, we followed two basic rules: firstly, cover the maximum number of regions or countries from EU-28 for each variable represented in maps or graphs and secondly, get the highest quality of data used for calculating indicators. However, to achieve our goals we were obliged to frame and manage distinct datasets in calculating indicators. Additionally, we had to make some important decisions concerning the selection of data in order to offer a comprehensive and clear visualization of data displayed in the different maps and graphs presented. Thus:

1. Sometimes, the lack of values throughout the time window being analysed, suggested depicting maps and graphs based on data referring to a particular year with the lowest number of missing values.
2. Some other times, the plethora of data in a time window led us to calculate the average for a concrete period of time (3-4 years) as the most adequate figure to be displayed.
3. Finally, for some particular sources, we have no other choice than using the full dataset including data from their origins up to now.

Details and particularities of sources and datasets compiled for calculating indicators are shown in table 1 exposed in the previous sections of this report.

1.3.4. Statistical and visualization techniques

This section deals with principal decisions made on the different statistical and visualization techniques used in this report.

On the one hand, *section 2* addresses the operationalization of the RegHealth-RI framework blocks, which has been performed through descriptive statistics and the development of geographical maps. The elaboration of maps and graphs will be especially useful when regional level analysis is performed, since data table for it are quite large. Additional graphs supporting and facilitating the analysis and visualization of the abundant data under study will also be presented if necessary. Descriptive statistics performed will include:

- Redesign, format and elaboration (if applicable) of data tables.
- Counting of frequencies and elaboration of graphs (if necessary).
- Calculation of position and dispersion measures: average, quartiles⁵.
- Information visualization: Geographical maps, bar graphics, scatter plots.

In *sections 3*, a more proper econometric analysis has been performed, starting with correlations on all principal variables and an Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) regression for assessing the determinants of Health publishing and Health patenting propensity at the NUTS2 level. As a minor remark, we recall that in a large part of the analysis, variables have been standardized per million population. Although this type of standardization may underestimate some large countries such as United

⁴ The idea behind this Global Observatory is to monitor and analyze relevant information on Health R&D, building on national and regional observatories (or equivalent functions) and existing global data collection mechanisms with a view to contributing to the identification of gaps and opportunities for health R&D (WHO, 2013).

⁵ With quartiles, total observations are divided in four equal groups. For instance, in the case of EU-28, the first group would include the top-7 countries, the second group the countries from the 8th to the 14th, and so on.

Kingdom, Germany or France, it represents an accepted and well-diffused methodology for countries comparison.

Finally, the geographical maps included in this report have been characterized with different shades of the colour to represent the distinct shares of the distribution that they are based on. The strongest shade expresses the best-performing cases of the distribution, which corresponds to the first quartile in the case of maps displaying quartiles.

1.3.5. Limitations of the analysis

Although the main goal of this report is to analyse the present situation of health R&I in EU regions and countries, a simple glance at table 1 may be enough to notice the main limitation to carry out this analysis: the lack of data with respect to (i) regional NUTS2 level, (ii) the specific sector of health or (iii) the combination of both cases. Whenever NUTS2 regional breakdown was not accessible, country-level data have been used. We are perfectly aware that strong intra-country differences do exist, but this strategy was chosen to provide the most extensive analysis possible. In other words, we have decided to provide a country comparison of national averages, complementing it with the exact regional distribution, where possible. To make an example, we anticipate here in graph 1 the case of FP7 project participation.

Graph 1 - FP7 Health projects participation, per million population: regional dispersion

Source: EC, CORDA

This figure clearly depicts the situation of many Health variables in the EU. Looking at the averages, the usual idea of a better performing Nordic Europe is confirmed. Countries like Finland, Sweden, Belgium and the Netherlands have better results than others (especially Southern and Eastern EU countries). However, couples of countries with a very similar average can have a completely different situation behind. We make two examples.

First, a good performing country as the Netherlands has a higher average than Denmark; however, the top Danish region achieves a maximum score of more than 140 projects per million population,

while the top Dutch one does not go beyond 120. Even more, the top region (London) belongs to a country (UK) whose average is not particularly high.

Second, a low performing country in terms of average, that is the Czech Republic, shows a top region that is in line with countries with higher averages (e.g. Slovenia and Ireland) and even above large countries (e.g. Italy).

Of course, having a low average might signal the strong unbalances that exist in some EU countries. As it will be shown throughout all *section 2* – especially when visualising European maps of Health R&I indicators – many countries have just one or two spots of better performance, as compared to a very poor environment in the rest of their territories. The joint analysis of the national and the NUTS2 regional level, then, is even more needed to depict the concentration and unbalances of Health R&I, in both top and least performing countries.

The difference in the availability of R&I data between national and regional indicators is not a novel issue. The most relevant example is represented by the national and regional rankings of innovativeness in the EU: the Innovation Union Scoreboard vs. the Regional Innovation Scoreboard⁶. The development of the regional innovation index cannot replicate 100% the one calculated at the national level, because of the lack of figures regarding almost all data categories: human resources; open, excellent and attractive research systems; finance and support; intellectual assets and economic effects, etc. In other words, it is not only the sector of Health specificity that brings problems in its measurement. Also the regionalisation of innovation data suffers for availability issues that at the EU level have not been solved yet.

One of the most crucial variables for the current report – that is R&D expenditures – is instead available, although not broken down by industrial sector, thus not allowing the focus on Health. Since some decades now, however, national statistical offices provide the regional breakdown of national R&D, following guidelines in the Frascati Manual (OECD, 2002). Such regionalisation of R&D will be extensively used in the next chapters.

Difficulties do instead arise when referring to private Health R&D. The Health R&D expenditure reported following the breakdown of Eurostat/OECD GERD, in fact, give only a very broad picture of financial flows for health R&D in the countries. Two main problems do exist: varying response rates to the health-related questions; varying final estimates depending on which proxies are selected. Furthermore, most users of these data take R&D expenditure by the pharmaceutical industry as a proxy for total Health R&D in the Business Enterprise sector. Indeed, R&D carried out by the pharmaceuticals industry is only one component of health-related R&D in the business sector. Another immediately identifiable manufacturing industry is Medical instruments but also the sum of these two figures might overestimate the performance of those countries where Health R&D expenditures are more related to services. Unfortunately, no breakdown of services related to Health exists in the Eurostat/OECD data (for further information on this issue, see OECD, 2001). Additional problems arise also for other data categories, such as when measuring university health R&D or clinical trials. Given all these problematic issues, for the purposes of the current report we decided to rely on the estimations of Health R&D and clinical trials provided for all world countries in a Lancet publication (Røttingen, J-A et al., 2013). Such estimations have been provided by the joint work of WHO, OECD and other international institutions, within the framework of the Global Observatory for Health R&D mentioned above.

In relation to the breakdown of data by sector, it seems obvious that because of the health specialization required in this report, only those variables with available data to calculate suitable

⁶ Data and reports of the two Scoreboards can be found at:
http://ec.europa.eu/growth/industry/innovation/facts-figures/scoreboards/index_en.htm

indicators focused on health were included. However, some exceptions have been done in relation to innovation component mainly due to a great scarcity of data in general, which is even more marked when a breakdown by health sector is intended. Thus, within the innovation component of this report we have included indicators of general scope such as innovation indices elaborated by the EC (*Innovation Union Scoreboard* at national level and *Regional Innovation Scoreboard* for regions), together with those specifically selected for measuring innovation performance on health sector, most of the times only available at country level.

Although it is not a primary objective of this report, it is well to refer to the particular limitations of the different variables being analysed in this report. Clear examples of these limitations are related, for instance, to publications. Problems like attribution of work done in joint and collaborative publications, impact calculation only based on citation or counting of citations without distinguishing among positive and negative citations, assignment of the same global impact factors of journals to individual publications in it, etc., have already been discussed by researchers and experts from some time ago to present date (McRoberts and McRoberts, 1989; Seglen, 1997; Cronin, 2001; Way and Ahmad, 2013; Hickset *al.*, 2015; International Committee of Medical Journal Editors, 2015). Similarly, limitations related to patents are also well-known and have also been pointed out, for instance, in a survey by International Monetary Fund (2015) where is stated that: “Patents have limitations as a measure of technology output because many inventions are never patented, a significant portion of technological knowledge remains tacit, and only a small number of patents account for most of the value”.

2. SITUATION OF HEALTH RESEARCH & INNOVATION IN EUROPE

2.1. Research & Innovation in EU Countries

2.1.1. R&I Inputs

2.1.1.1. Expenditures

2.1.1.1.1. R&D Expenditure (I1)

Map 2 – R&D Investment at National Level - Health GERD (% on GDP)

Own elaboration from Røttingen et al. (2013). Year: 2010 or latest years when not available

As shown in Map 2, the highest shares of gross domestic expenditure on research and development (GERD) are for EU Northern countries, including Sweden, Denmark, UK and central EU countries such as Germany, Netherlands and Belgium. Surprisingly, Slovenia also appears as one of the leading countries.

Map 3 – R&D Investment at National level - R&D Expenditure of pharmaceutical industry (Million Euros by million population)

Source: Own elaboration EFPIA key data (2015). Data refer to year 2013; for Czech Republic, Denmark, France, Hungary data refer to year 2012; for Austria, Croatia, Netherlands data refer to year 2011.

Source: EFP IA member associations (official Maps)

In Map 3, it is confirmed the relevance of Nordic countries when referring to pharmaceuticals R&D expenditures. Data weighted by population, instead than by GDP, decrease the performance of larger countries such as Germany or the UK.

2.1.1.2. Human Resources
2.1.1.2.1. Total R&D Personnel (I2)

Map 4 – Actors and activities at National level – HEALTH GOVERD + HERD R&D personnel (FTE) by Million population

Source: Own elaboration EUROSTAT data (year: 2011)

In Map 4, the relevance of Nordic countries is confirmed when looking at Health R&D expenditures by Government and Universities. Southern (Spain and Greece) and Eastern EU countries show a better performance than in the previous maps. However, this map is negatively affected by missing data for some key countries such as France or the UK.

2.1.1.2.2. Researchers (I3)

Map 5 – Actors and activities at National level – HEALTH GOVERD + HERD researchers (FTE) by Million population

Source: Own elaboration EUROSTAT data (year: 2011)

In Map 5, data limitations prevent from giving a comprehensive overview of public and university researchers in Health. Among the available countries, also Portugal shows a good performance, together with the countries already highlighted in the previous map.

2.1.2.1.2. Health Clusters (15)

Map 7 – Actors and activities at National level – Number of Clusters including activities on Health, Biotech, Medical and Pharmaceuticals

Source: Own elaboration data from Cluster Observatory (Year: 2016)

In Map 7 it is reported the number of clusters including Health activities in the EU countries. Besides the largest ones, the best performance appears also in Hungary. Among Widening countries, a good performance is also reported in the case of Poland and Estonia.

2.1.2.1.3. Science Parks (I6)

Map 8 – Actors and activities at National level – Number of Science Parks including activities on Health, Biotech, Medical and Pharmaceuticals

Source: Own elaboration data from Cluster Observatory (Year: 2016)

A similar picture is reported in Map 8 concerning the number of science parks including Health activities. In this case, only France, Spain and Sweden replicate the top performance of the previous map. Italy and Finland also appear as top performers, while Estonia confirms its performance among Widening countries.

2.1.2.2. Higher Education Institutions and Public Research Organizations

2.1.2.2.1. Active Medical Schools (17)

Map 9 – Actors and activities at National level - Higher Education Institutions – Number of Active Medical schools

Source: Own elaboration IMED (FAIMER) data (Year: updated 2015)

Map 9 reports the absolute values of active medical schools. The ranking clearly follows the size of countries, also among Widening ones, as in the case of Poland and Romania.

2.1.2.2.2. Active Pharmacy Schools (I8)

Map 10 – Actors and activities at National level - Higher Education Institutions - Number of Active Pharmacy schools

Source: Own elaboration fip.org data (Year: updated 2015)

Map 10 shows a similar picture to the previous one, moving the attention to active pharmacy schools. In the second group of countries, it can be noticed the presence of Widening countries such as Hungary and Portugal.

2.1.2.3. Knowledge Flows

2.1.2.3.1. Intra-country Health Co-publications (I9)

Map 11 – Knowledge flow at National level – Intra-country Health co-publications (by population)

Source: Own elaboration EC-DG-RTD Framework contract (Year: Average 2008-2012)

As highlighted in Map 11, the collaboration in publications within each country is much higher in Northern EU countries, ranging from Ireland to Scandinavian countries.

2.1.2.3.2. International Health Co-publications (I10)

Map 12 – Knowledge flows at National level – International Health co-publications (by population)

Source: Own elaboration EC-DG-RTD Framework contract (Year: Average 2008-2012)

In Map 12, collaboration in publications regards only their international degree. In this case, some top countries of the previous map decrease their performance, while others improve, especially Austria.

2.1.2.3.3. Intra-country Health Co-patents (I11)

Map 13 – Knowledge flows at National level – Intra-country Health co-patents (by population)

Source: Own elaboration EC-DG-RTD Framework contract (Year: Average 2008-2010)

In Map 13, it is reported collaboration in patents within each country. In this case, the ranking reflects the industrial specialisation of countries, with top performance of Austria, Denmark, Germany, Ireland, the Netherlands and Sweden. Among Widening countries, only Slovenia appears in this top group.

2.1.2.3.4. International Health Co-patents (I12)

Map 14 – Knowledge flows at National level – International Health co-patents with Third Countries by population

Source: Own elaboration EC-DG-RTD Framework contract (Year: Average 2008-2010)

In Map 14, moving to the international (non-EU) degree of co-patenting, large countries like France and the UK are back in the top group. All Widening countries appear in the least performing group, as a confirmation of their limited involvement in patent collaboration.

2.1.3. R&I Outputs

2.1.3.1. New R&I Human Resources

2.1.3.1.1. PhD students (ISCED level 6) (I13)

Map 15 – New R&I human resources – PhD students – Second stage of tertiary education (level 6) in Health by million population

Source: Own elaboration EUROSTAT data (Year: average 2008-2012)

Map 15 shows the number of Health PhD students by population. Besides Scandinavian countries, the top performance is reported also in Widening countries such as Romania and Slovakia. In general, this map is deviating strongly from the previous ones, confirming that advanced education follows a different path as compared to R&I inputs.

2.1.3.2. R&I Infrastructures

2.1.3.2.1. Research Infrastructures (I14)

Map 16 – R&I infrastructure at National level – Number of Health (domain: Biological and Medical Sciences) research infrastructures

Source: Own elaboration MERIL data (Year: updated 2016)

The absolute number of Health research infrastructures reported in Map 16 confirms the best performance of Western EU countries, including Portugal and Spain. In the second group, a good performance is also appearing for Hungary and Slovenia.

2.1.3.3. Knowledge Creation

2.1.3.3.1. Peer-reviewed Publications (I15)

Map 17 – Knowledge creation at National level – Health publications fractional count (by population)

Source: Own elaboration EC-DG-RTD Framework contract (Year: Average 2008-2012)

Map 17 confirms that the highest values of Health publications, even weighted by population, are found in Northern EU countries. This Map is very similar to Maps 10 and 11, confirming that the overall propensity to publish is highly correlated with collaboration in publications.

2.1.3.3.2. Top Publications (I16)

Map 18 – Knowledge creation at National level – Percentage of Top-10% Health Most Highly Cited Publications (FRAC)

Source: Own elaboration EC-DG-RTD Framework contract (Year: Average 2008-2009)

Selecting only the most highly cited publications, in Map 18, a very similar picture comes out, with two exceptions: Ireland falls to the second group of countries, while Austria goes up to the top one. Among Widening countries, it can be noticed the good performance of Estonia.

2.1.3.3.3. Patent Applications (I17)

Map 19 – Knowledge creation at National level – Health EPO patent applications (average 2008-2010) by country of inventor (by population)

Source: Own elaboration EC-DG-RTD Framework contract (Year: Average 2008-2010)

Moving to patent applications, in Map 19 appears how this indicator is strongly correlated with the Health industrial specialisation of EU countries. Almost all non-Widening countries are included in the top two groups, while Widening countries in the least two group. The only exception is represented by Slovenia.

2.1.3.4. New Products and Processes
2.1.3.4.1. On-going Clinical Trials (I18)

Map 20 – New products and processes at National level – Number of On-going Clinical Trials (by population)

Source: Own elaboration CenterWatch Database (Year: 2015)

Map 20 shows the countries with the highest number of on-going clinical trials, weighted by population. Also this map presents a very differentiated evidence: in the top group, for the first time it is included Bulgaria together with other Widening countries like Hungary and Estonia, besides most industrialised ones like Austria, Belgium, Denmark and Germany.

2.1.4. Performance in EU Research Framework Programmes

2.1.4.1. EU Funded Project Participation

2.1.4.1.1. Participation in FP7 Projects (119)

Map 21 – Performance in EU research framework programmes at national level – Health FP7 project participated (by population)

Source: Own elaboration CORDA (EC) (all FP7 period)

Map 21 shows the countries with the highest number of funded FP7 projects in Health, weighted by population. Largest countries show a worse performance, due to their size in population. Good performances are reported by Estonia, but also by Hungary and Slovenia, among Widening countries.

2.1.4.1.2. Participation in H2020 Projects (I20)

Map 22 – Performance in EU research framework programmes at national level – Health Horizon 2020 project funded (by population)

Source: Own elaboration CORDA (EC)

Map 22 shows the countries with the highest number of funded Horizon 2020 projects in Health. The picture is slightly different from the FP7 one, but it has to be recalled that results of Horizon 2020 project calls are still preliminary.

Map 23 – Performance in EU research framework programmes at national level – Health Horizon 2020 project applications (by population)

Source: Own elaboration CORDA (EC)

Map 23 shows Horizon 2020 Health project applications. Also in this case, the highly differentiated situation in the EU reflects preliminary data and the weighting by population. It is confirmed, among Widening countries, the good performance of Estonia and Slovenia.

Map 24 – Performance in EU research framework programmes at national level – Health Horizon 2020 Success Rate (project funded/project applications)

Source: Own elaboration CORDA (EC)

Looking in Map 24 at Horizon 2020 success rates, for the first time the highest rates regard Widening countries, with top performance found in Croatia, Estonia, Latvia and Slovakia, besides Austria and Sweden.

2.1.5. Innovation Component

2.1.5.1. Innovation Performance

2.1.5.1.1. Innovation Union Scoreboard (I21)

Map 25 – Innovation Union Scoreboard 2015

Source: EC, DG Internal Market, Industry, Entrepreneurship and SMEs

Map 25 recalls the results of the innovation Union Scoreboard, with EU countries broken down in: Leading Innovators, Innovation followers, Moderate Innovators and Modest Innovators. With the exception of Slovenia, it is confirmed that countries in the two top categories are all non-Widening countries.

2.1.5.1.3. Granted Patents (I22)

Map 26 – Innovation performance at National level – Health EPO patent granted (average 2008-2010) by country of inventor (by population)

Source: Own elaboration EC-DG-RTD Framework contract (Year: Average 2008-2012)

To complement the evidence on patent applications, in Map 26 it is reported the countries with the highest number of Health patents granted. Results confirm those of Map 18, with top performances in Central and Northern EU countries: Austria, Denmark, France, Germany, the Netherlands and Sweden.

2.1.5.1.4. SME Instrument Applicants (I23)

Map 27 – Innovation performance at National level – Number of Horizon 2020 SME project applicants (by population)

Source: Own elaboration CORDA (EC)

To complement the evidence on Horizon 2020, Map 27 shows that the SME instrument is used in both Widening and non-Widening countries. Top numbers of applicants are found in Denmark, Estonia, Finland, Hungary, the Netherlands and Slovenia.

2.1.5.1.5. SME Instrument Success (I24)

Map 28 – Innovation performance at National level – Number of Horizon 2020 SME funded applicants (by population)

Source: Own elaboration CORDA (EC)

Map 28 complements the previous one looking at the funded projects under Horizon 2020 SME. Excluding Hungary and Slovenia, results confirm the top ranking for SME applicants, with also the inclusion of Ireland in the top group.

2.2. Research & Innovation in EU Regions

2.2.1. R&I Actors and Activities

2.2.1.1. Business Enterprise Sector

2.2.1.1.1. Health Clusters (15)

Map 29 – Actors and activities at Nuts2 level – Number of Clusters including activities on Health, Biotech, Medical and Pharmaceuticals

Source: Own elaboration data from Cluster Observatory (Year: 2016)

Map 29 identifies the EU regions with the highest number of clusters including Health activities. It can be noticed that top performances belong not only to most advanced regions, but also to those in Widening countries. It has to be underlined, however, that the number of clusters in itself might be misleading. Some top EU regions might therefore be underestimated in this data source.

Map 30 – Actors and activities at Nuts2 level – Flag for Clusters related to Health sectors

Source: Own elaboration EU Cluster Observatory data (Year: 2016). Flag for regions with at least one cluster related to Health sectors (Including Biotech).

To compensate the data limitations highlighted in the previous map, Map 30 shows the regions that have at least one Health cluster. This map confirms that clusters – although more present in advanced countries such as France, Germany or Sweden – are more equally distributed over Europe, than other variables (e.g. the R&I input and output ones).

2.2.1.1.2. Science Parks (I6)

Map 31 – Actors and activities at Nuts2 level - Number of Science Parks including activities on Health, Biotech, Medical and Pharmaceuticals

Source: Own elaboration data from Cluster Observatory (Year: 2016)

Map 31 shows similar evidence, highlighting the presence of Science Parks including Health activities. In comparison with clusters, some regions lose strength (e.g. the German ones), while others increase their performance (e.g. the Spanish ones). Some Widening regions are still included in the top group (e.g. in the Baltic countries).

Map 32 – Actors and activities at NUTS2 level – Flag for Health Science parks

Source: Own elaboration EU Cluster Observatory data (Year: 2016). Flag for regions with at least one science park related to Health sectors (including Biotech)

As in the case of clusters, also for Science Parks it is presented a simplified version in Map 32. Flagging EU regions with at least one Health Science Park, it is shown that such a technological strategy is still spread over Europe, but less used than the presence of clusters.

2.2.1.2. Higher Education Institutions and Public Research Organizations

2.2.1.2.1. Active Medical Schools (17)

Map 33 – Actors and activities at NUTS 2 level – Number Higher Education Institutions – Number of Active Medical schools

Source: Own elaboration IMED (FAIMER) data (Year: updated 2015)

Looking, in Map 33, at Medical Schools, it can be noticed that top regions are concentrated in very few countries (e.g. France, Italy and Spain). However, many EU regions are listed in the second group (those with 2 medical schools), and this applies to both Widening and non-Widening countries.

2.2.1.2.2. Active Pharmacy Schools (I8)

Map 34 – Actors and activities at NUTS 2 level - Higher Education Institutions – Number of Active Pharmacy schools

Source: Own elaboration fip.org data (Year: updated 2015)

Similarly to the previous one, Map 34 confirms that also Pharmacy Schools are concentrated in few countries, although in this case the strength of Widening countries' regions is higher (e.g. in the case of Latvia, Poland, Portugal and Romania).

2.2.1.3. Knowledge Flows

2.2.1.3.1. Intra-country Health Co-patents (I11)

Map 35 – Knowledge flows at NUTS2 level – Intra-country Health co-patents (by population)

Source: Own elaboration EC-DG-RTD Framework contract (Year: Average 2008-2010)

Looking at intra-country co-patenting at the regional level, and comparing it with Map 12, in Map 35 two distinct phenomena are highlighted. On the one side, the strength of some countries resides in the concentration of co-patents in few regions (e.g. for Finland, France, Italy or Spain). On the other side, the strength of other countries (like Germany, Ireland or the UK) derives from a wider dispersion on the national territory. In Widening countries, very few regions present a satisfactory performance, while the majority are least performing regions.

2.2.1.3.2. International Health Co-patents (I12)

Map 36 – Knowledge flows at NUTS2 level – Flag for regions with International Health co-patents with Third Countries by population

Source: Own elaboration EC-DG-RTD Framework contract (Year: Average 2008-2010). The color indicates only that those regions have co-patenting with Third countries.

The situation depicted in the previous map is confirmed in Map 36. Here, only regions where Health co-patenting with Third (non-EU) countries are coloured. The Map clearly shows that the most advanced co-patenting is a prerogative of very few regions, all belonging to most advanced countries.

2.2.2. R&I Outputs

2.2.2.1. R&I Infrastructures

2.2.2.1.1. Research Infrastructures (I14)

Map 37 – R&I infrastructure at NUTS2 level – Number of Health (domain: Biological and Medical Sciences) research infrastructures

Source: Own elaboration MERIL data (Year: updated 2016)

Map 37 shows the distribution of Health research infrastructure across EU regions. In this case, performances strongly vary both in Widening and non-Widening countries. In the large majority of cases, top performances in each country are very concentrated in few regions (a notable exception is represented by French regions).

2.2.2.2. Knowledge Creation

2.2.2.2.1. Peer-reviewed Publications (I15)

Map 38 – Knowledge creation at NUTS2 level – Health publications fractional count (by population)

Source: Own elaboration EC-DG-RTD Framework contract (Year: Average 2008-2012)

Map 38 shows the number of Health publications by population across EU regions. Also in this case, the best performances of some countries derive from a wide dispersion in their regions (e.g. for Finland, Germany or the UK); while for other countries there is a much higher degree of concentration (e.g. in France and Spain). Regions belonging to Widening countries are generally performing worse, although some of them enter in the second top group (e.g. regions in Croatia, Czech Republic, Hungary and Poland).

2.2.2.2. Patent Applications (I17)

Map 39 – Knowledge creation at NUTS2 level – Health EPO patent applications (average 2008-2010) by region of inventor (by population)

Source: Own elaboration EC-DG-RTD Framework contract (Year: Average 2008-2010)

In Map 39, it is presented another R&I output at the regional level, that is the number of patent applications by population. In this case, the degree of concentration in Central and Northern EU regions is very high, in parallel with the industrial specialisation of these territories. With very few exceptions, Widening countries' regions belong only to the two lowest quartiles in the distribution, showing a worse situation than in the case of publications.

2.2.2.3. New Products and Processes
2.2.2.3.1. On-going Clinical Trials (I18)

Map 40 – New products and processes at NUTS2 level – Number of On-going Clinical Trials (by population)

Source: Own elaboration CenterWatch Database (Year: 2015)

If we look, in Map 40, at on-going clinical trials in EU regions, we can notice a wider dispersion in Europe and a better performance of Eastern EU regions. Top performance is, for instance, associated with almost the entire Hungary and also Bulgarian regions perform high (in contrast with all previous maps). Top performance is also appearing in many German regions and in all Denmark.

Map 41 – New products and processes at NUTS2 level – Number of On-going Clinical Trials

Source: Own elaboration CenterWatch Database (Year: updated 2015)

In order to control the bias in favour of countries with less population, in Map 41 we present the absolute values of clinical trials (not weighted by population). Many regions still present the top performance, both in Widening and non-Widening countries. However, a very high number of clinical trials is now found in several French, Italian, Polish and Spanish regions.

2.2.3. Performance in EU Research Framework Programmes

2.2.3.1. EU Funded Project Participation

2.2.3.1.1. Participation in FP7 Projects (119)

Map 42 – Performance in EU research framework programmes at NUTS2 level – Health FP7 project participated (by population)

Source: Own elaboration CORDA (EC) (all FP7 period)

Map 42 depicts the participation to Health FP7 projects across EU regions. In non-Widening countries, there are differences between countries with very concentrated performances (France and Spain) and countries with a more widespread participation (Germany, Italy, the Netherlands, Sweden and the UK). On the contrary, in Widening countries the few good performances are always associated with a high degree of concentration in one or few regions.

2.2.4. Innovation Component
2.2.4.1. Innovation Performance
2.2.4.1.1. Regional Innovation Scoreboard (I21)

Map 43 – Regional Innovation Scoreboard 2014

Source: EC, DG Internal Market, Industry, Entrepreneurship and SMEs (former Enterprise and Industry)

Map 43 recalls the outcome of the EU Regional Innovation Scoreboard. Regions considered Innovation leaders are all belonging to non-Widening countries, while the worst performing regions (modest innovators) are all belonging to Widening countries, with only few exceptions, like Illes Balears in Spain.

3. ANALYSIS OF HEALTH RESEARCH & INNOVATION IN EUROPE

3.1. Detection of common patterns and analysis of key variables on Health R&I within the less performing EU regions

3.1.1. A preliminary analysis at the country-level

In order to detect some common patterns and key variables of Health R&I in Europe both knowledge creation and knowledge transfer have not been analysed only in their own, but also in relation with some possible influencing factors (see input variables reported in table 1). As explained in the methodological section we faced some limitations in finding all possible data for measuring such influencing factors (particularly variables related to the specific sector of Health). We used all possible variables for which reliable information does exist as well as variables related to Health gross domestic expenditure in R&D (GERD) and related to on-going clinical trials recently estimated and published in Lancet (Røttingen, J-A et al., 2013). Correlation between outcome variables (knowledge creation, knowledge transfer, projects) and main determinants such as R&D expenditure variables, R&D personnel variables, infrastructure variables and trials have been run. Among all the variables we report here the ones with the strongest coefficients of correlation. Also in this case we use relative measures normalizing all the variables by million population. We want to stress, anyway, that in the use of absolute values we detected better performance of larger countries and stronger correlation coefficients.

First of all, correlating scientific outcome (publications) with R&D expenditure we found that Health GERD by Lancet and Health GOVERD + HERD measured by Eurostat have the strongest coefficients. In doing the analysis we noticed also that this correlation changes if we distinguish between Widening and Non-Widening countries. Graphs 2 and 3 that report the correlations of the outcome publications with the two mentioned variables for the two groups of countries show indeed a *weaker correlation for Widening countries*, but also that *some countries of this group make a “most efficient” use of scarce resources* with respect to Non-Widening countries (i.e. high number of publications with a much smaller amount of expenditure). The small graph in the grey area reported on graph 3 shows that this is valid also when the correlation is done considering human resources (that is the number of Human Resources in Science and Technology⁷ by population, instead of the R&D expenditures variable).

⁷ Persons with tertiary education (ISCED) and/or employed in science and technology, In Eurostat they correspond to [hrst_st_nsec2], Age: From 15 to 74 years.

Graph 2- Total Health R&D expenditure and Health publications (years 2008-2012)

Graph 3- Public and University Health R&D expenditure and Health publications (years 2008-2012)

It is possible to obtain a similar picture also correlating R&D expenditures with the number of intra-country co-publications (Graph 4).

Graph 4- Total Health R&D expenditure and Health co-publications

In graph 5 we correlate Health GERD with international co-publications: results show that when related to international collaboration, the behaviour of Non-Widening countries varies quite substantially (the dispersion is higher than for Widening countries). Some countries, such as Italy, Spain and Greece, result to have a much more similar behaviour of Widening countries.

Graph 5- Total Health R&D expenditure and Health co-publications

Very much in line with these correlations is also the correlation obtained when the variable used to correlate with Health co-publication is the Health GOVERD + HERD by Eurostat (Graph 6).

Graph 6- Public and University Health R&D expenditure and Health co-publications

Let’s now take a look at the main variables of input we have identified and the relation with innovation (patents). Graph 7 shows the correlation of number of patents with Health GERD reported by Lancet. Since we want to focus on other aspects of the analysis we don’t show here the distinction between Widening and Non-Widening that is pretty much the same as it is for publication. As we can observe from the graph there is for sure a strong correlation among patents and the general R&D expenditure in Health. Nevertheless, what this graph is not able to say is if this is something that depends on the private or public R&D expenditure. As mentioned in the methodological part, some variables as the Eurostat BERD (Business enterprise expenditure in R&D) cannot be considered a good proxy to use in the Health sector for evaluating business R&D investments. For this reason we tried to use alternative measures and in particular the estimation of R&D expenditure by the European Federation of Pharmaceutical industries and associations (EFPIA) –although this indicator is not available for all countries).

Graph 7-Total Health R&D expenditure and Health patents

Graphs 8 and 9 show therefore respectively how patents correlate with the public and private expenditure. Apparently the public expenditure (measured as Health GOVERD + HERD) seems to have a better explanatory power than the private expenditure. We need nevertheless to consider that with this exercise we are not able to detect the causal relation between the two variables and also that this correlation coefficient is indeed weaker than the coefficient obtained with the use of Health variable GERD by Lancet.

Graph 8 - Business Health R&D expenditure and Health patents

Graph 9 - Public and University Health R&D expenditure and Health patents

After having selected the best correlation at country level we checked the availability of the best correlations also at regional level.

The variables that correlate better with publications and total co-publications result to be: in terms of R&D investment, the variable Health GOVERD+HERD; while in terms of Human resources the variable R&D personnel by Eurostat (head count). These variables have weaker correlation (in terms of strength of the relation) if we compare them with those at country level. In other words, *intra-country regional differences might reduce the overall effect* (see table 3) between input and output variables.

We notice also that these variables correlate even better with co-publications, but we need to consider that at regional level the data on co-publications are available only for the 50 most publishing regions, are not fractional and do not distinguish among intra-country and international collaborations. For this reason it is not possible to make a direct comparison with national level and the analysis at regional level may be strongly biased.

The variables that instead seem to correlate better with patents are Health Business R&D expenditure and Health Business R&D personnel (considered in terms of full time equivalents) (see again table 3).

To conclude *correlations calculated at the regional level confirm the results found at the national level, although the coefficients are weaker*. A deeper analysis is needed, as shown in the next subsection.

Table 3 – Comparison of correlations at regional and country level

Outcomes	National Public and University R&D	Regional Public and University R&D	National R&D personnel	Regional R&D personnel	National Business R&D	Regional Business R&D	National Business R&D personnel	Regional Business R&D personnel
Publications	0.8087***	0.4773***	0.7452***	0.3979***				
Co-publications	0.7392***	0.6336***	0.6827***	0.5010***				
Patents					0.7935***	0.6132***	0.8014***	0.5203***
Co-patents					0.6994***	0.5838***	0.7461***	0.5031***

3.1.2. Which are the less performing EU regions in Health R&I?

Before looking for the determinants of high and low Health R&I performance, we try to summarise all the evidence shown in section 3 through a comparative exercise. Table 4 highlights in absolute values which are the less performing regions both for the R&I outcomes patents and publications, but also in terms of clinical trials and medical infrastructures related to medical schools and pharmacy schools. Since it was not possible to analyse different years for clinical trials and schools we opted to consider for all the variables the last available year of data⁸. The order of the countries mirrors the last ten positions in terms of performances. Comparing table 4, which considers the absolute numbers, with table 5, which normalizes the performances in terms of population, we can notice that there are substantial changes in the position of some countries. The disadvantage of some small countries such as Cyprus or Malta in table 4, for example, it is not present in table 5. Although most of the countries with worst position are widening countries, we notice that particularly in relation to the infrastructures some countries such as Denmark, Netherlands or Germany have among the worst performances in terms of numbers of schools (see table 5). This shows that after all for performing well in R&I what counts probably is the quality of the research conducted in institutes and not the number of institutes.

Table 4 – Comparison of less performing countries (in absolute values)

Rank	HealthPatents	Health Publications	Clinical Trials	Medicalschools	Pharmacyschools
....					
20	CY	LV	MT	LU	LU
21	MT	MT	CY	MT	MT
22	RO	LU	LU	EE	EE
23	EE	CY	SI	CY	SI
24	BG	EE	EE	SI	LT
25	LT	LT	LT	LT	SK
26	SK	BG	LV	LV	DK
27	LU	SI	IE	SK	HR
28	HR	SK	HR	DK	BG

⁸ 2010 for patents, 2012 for publications and 2015 for all others variables

Table 5 – Comparison of less performing countries (values by million inhabitants)

Rank	HealthPatents	Health Publications	Clinical Trials	Medicalschools	Pharmacyschools
.....					
20	RO	LV	MT	LU	DK
21	BG	RO	CY	PL	NL
22	SK	BG	LU	HU	SK
23	PL	LT	SI	DE	CZ
24	LT	CY	PT	AT	HR
25	EL	SK	IE	NL	BG
26	EE	EE	RO	UK	DE
27	PT	HU	HR	DK	PL
28	CZ	PL	LT	SK	LT

The graph below considers then the last 25 performing regions for Health publications, Health patents, clinical trials and medical schools standardized by population (please see in the appendix a detail list of those regions⁹. The regions that are highlighted in the map (graph 10) are those with the worst performances, with a difference: regions highlighted in dark blue have low performance in outputs and are not specialized in the Health sector; regions highlighted in light blue have low performance despite being specialized in Health¹⁰. This an important issue to take into consideration, as it shows that some regions, which have invested more in Health than in other sectors, might have not fully exploited their potentiality.

Graph 10 – Map of less performing regions at NUTS2 level

Health Publications by population

Health Patents by population

Own elaboration EC DG-RTD (Framework contract)

⁹ Since more than one region share the same position for some of the variables such as number of medical schools, to prioritize the order of the positions, we first considered the position of the region in terms of publications performance and only after the position with respect to all the other variables.

¹⁰ The specialization index (calculated on 5 years, 2008-2012) in the Health sector is higher than 1 for those regions which have relatively more publications and/or patents in Health as compared to other macro-sectors.

On-going Clinical trials by population

Own elaboration CenterWatch Database

Medical schools by population

Own elaboration FAIMER (IMED) data

3.1.3. A deeper look at the regional determinants of Health R&I

To investigate the potential relationship of the most relevant indicators which may have an effect on Health R&I outputs, we perform some correlations.

Similar to the analysis performed in the Science Metrix report on cross cutting analysis of scientific publications versus other science indicators (European Commission, 2013) we developed a correlation matrix of the relationships between different pairs of indicators. Each indicator is the result of a careful selection among all the Health regional variables related to S&T and other variables which are linked to the RegHealth-RI framework. The variables have been selected principally because they proxy different blocks of the framework as well due to their good availability at regional level for the years considered.

The following graph represents a matrix with a visualization of the correlations done with histograms. All the correlations among the different variables considered are statistically significant at 5% level (** $p < 0.05$). The bars in the histograms present in each cell indicate the intensity of the correlation of each pair of variables expressed in quintiles (higher number of bars = higher correlation intensity).

What emerges very clearly from graph 11 is that all R&I outcomes (which include patents, publications and clinical trials) correlate strongly with the variable related to human resources in science and technology. Publications and clinical trials are also strongly correlated with R&D personnel at the university. Important seems also for publications outcome the participation in international and domestic networks. While patents correlate well with business R&D expenditures, publications correlate not only well with all types of R&D expenditure but in particular with R&D in high education (HERD).

Graph 11 – Correlation matrix among variables

All measures are expressed in logarithmic terms with the exclusion of medical schools and clusters. The years have been selected in relation to availability, number of observations internal coherence and coherence with the regression models presented in the following section. Outputs variables such as patents and publications as well as external conditions refers to year 2010, input variables refer instead to the previous year 2009 (with the exclusion of the variable of Health FP7 participation which cover the entire period of FP7. On-going clinical trials can be related only to year 2015. Business R&D expenditure (million) n= 241; Public R&D expenditure (million) 216; University R&D expenditure (million) = 221; Human Resources in S&T (n. of persons with tertiary education (ISCED) and/or employed in science and technology) = 266; Business R&D personnel (FTE) n = 241; Public R&D personnel (FTE) n = 212; University R&D personnel (FTE) = 218; medical schools (number) n = 266; international Health collaboration (Health EPO co-patenting with 3rd countries) n= 266; domestic Health collaboration (Health EPO co-patenting) n = 214; Health FP7 projects (number) n. = 228; Health patents (Health EPO patents) n =224; Health publications (FRAC) = 266; on-going clinical trials (numbers) n = 261; population n = 264; GDP (million) n = 245; Wage (Wages and salaries - basic pharmaceutical products) n. = 144; biopharmaceutical cluster (only top) = 266; Medical device cluster (only top) n= 266.

The relevance of the relation between R&D expenditure in the region and R&I outcomes becomes even more evident if we consider a correlation of patents and publications with the average of the previous 5 years of R&D expenditures. Table below confirms that R&D expenditure (that have usually a more public nature) correlates more intensively with publications, while patents more with business R&D expenditure.

Table 6 - Correlation coefficient between different typology of expenditure in R&D and patents and publications propensity

R&D expenditure	Health Patents	Health Publications
BERD R&D (n. 83)	0.7555	0.6140
GOVERD R&D (n. 113)	0.5640	0.6956
HERD 0509 (n. 116)	0.6006	0.8666

Own elaboration EU DG data and EUROSTAT data. BERD (business expenditure in R&D), GOVERD (government expenditure in R&D) and HERD (higher educational R&D expenditure) are calculated on the average of previous 5 years to the referred year 2010 for patents and publications. All variables are in log terms. Correlations are significant at 1% level.

In general, public and private R&D expenditure as well as the number of personnel in the region involved in science and technology or dedicated to higher educational R&D seem to be (together with networking activities) the most important factors relating to R&I outcomes.

Another important point that emerges from the graph 11 (and that confirms the analysis performed in this report at national level) is that size (expressed here both in terms of population and GDP) has a certain important relation with the R&I outcomes of regions. We need also to consider that differential in wage may be relevant when considering regional output performances.

Are anyway those results and in general those correlations among input and output factors in graph 11 valid for all type of regions or do we observe differences when considering less performing regions? A deeper look at the correlation matrix for different typologies of less performing regions (regions belonging to Widening countries, regions with lower specialization in the Health sectors and regions with lower performances in patenting and publishing) may provide some useful insights on this respect.

The following matrix (graph 12) shows differences in terms of correlations for regions belonging only to Widening countries. The arrow in each cell shows if the coefficient of the correlation is higher or lower with respect to the correlation on graph 11. Green arrow represents higher coefficients for Widening regions, while red arrow a lower coefficient. The number indicated in the highlighted cells represents the delta with respect the correlation in graph 11.

For the matrix related to Widening countries we observe a higher correlation of patenting activities with public support and university infrastructures (schools and personnel) and lower correlation with R&D expenditure (particularly business) and participation in international network. For regions in Widening countries it seems therefore that it is more important to invest in university infrastructure and university R&D personnel for sustaining R&I outcomes more than increasing the R&D expenditure capacity which may probably need to reach a certain level of critical mass before to become a good driver for sustaining higher regional performances. The participation in network is then probably less developed in those countries and therefore may have less influence on Health patents regional performances.

It is also possible to observe that clinical trials in Widening countries are more related to the size of the region and GDP. One can guess that only big regions in those countries have the resources to conduct a certain number of clinical studies.

Graph 12 - Relevant differences for Widening Regions

The next graphs shows differences not only based on ex ante definitions (Widening vs. Non-Widening Countries), but on specific performance capacities in the Health sector. Graph 13 highlights differences for regions which have less specialization in Health sectors. The matrix is based on correlations of only regions that belong to the first quartile of the Health specialization index (the tail of less performing). As it is possible to notice in **less specialized regions** there is an evident lower relation of R&I outcomes with participation in Health networks (particularly in relation to publication). We can suppose - from the direction of the arrow related to Health collaboration - that what is needed in those regions it is a better support to link the regional activities with knowledge produced elsewhere (so if a region is not specialized in Health sector one of the possibilities to increase performances is to create policies favoring the acquisition of part of the knowledge externally). In this matrix emerges also that on-going clinical trials are less related to R&D expenditure (particularly in relation to higher educational R&D). We can find also a lower relation of on-going clinical trials with University personnel. This probably indicates a lack of public investment in those regions in relation to the Health sector.

Graph 13 - Relevant differences for Less Health specialised Regions

Graph 14 shows instead the correlation matrix for less **Health publishing regions** represented by the first quartile of regions (tail of less performing) in terms of number of EPO patents publications for the year 2010.

We notice that the correlation with university R&D expenditure and personnel is much weaker than in graph 15. Much weaker is also the correlation of Health publications with Health participation in FP7 projects. Since it may be difficult to provide those regions with the minimum amount of R&D investment to sustain a certain level of research activities, it seems that in the less publishing regions as in the case of less specialized regions a better support of networking may help to increase publication performances.

Graph 14 - Relevant differences for Less Health publishing Regions

Finally graph 15 shows the correlation matrix for **less Health patenting regions** in which it is the correlation of patents (and to a minor extent publications) with business R&D investments and R&D personnel that is weaker. It may be that for increasing R&I performances in those regions a certain critical mass of business R&D in those regions is required. Although medical schools in these regions may be of support of publications and clinical studies, they seems not being of any support for patenting activities. Again we notice that a weaker correlation exist of R&I outcomes with the activities of networking at international and national level, activities that should be wise to increase if they may guaranties a certain learning capabilities for improving R&I performances of actors in these typologies of regions (a capabilities that we saw require otherwise an increase of business R&D investments much above the usual established EU rates).

Graph 15 - Relevant differences for Less Health patenting Regions

3.2. Determinants of Health publishing propensity at the EU regional level

The correlations matrix presented in the previous section provides a first simple picture of what can be the potential relationship of the most relevant input indicators with the R&I outputs. However a correlation matrix exercise such this one or the one conducted in the science matrix report (European Commission, 2013) provide only some first indications on the relation among pair of factors. Understanding instead what can be a relation among R&I outcomes and input factors when different factors are in place require different econometric techniques.

In this section we perform a regression analysis to investigate the determinants of one of the most important outcomes of knowledge creation (Health publications) which is more closely related to the scientific and public aspects of knowledge (Dasgupta & David 1987, 1994; Callon, 1994). We will then confront this analysis with the analysis of determinants of another outcome of knowledge creation for which we have the same availability of data (Health patents). We take into consideration simultaneously a certain numbers of input and institutional factors, which are parts of the different RegHealth-RI framework blocks and that are considered strategic determinants in the literature when investigating R&I.

Indeed, there is a quite substantial literature in innovation studies investigating the knowledge creation capacity of firms and industries in relation to a wide range of determinants, including: R&D expenditure, quality of human resources, available infrastructures, degree of internationalization and collaborations, the composition and specialization of the industry as well as quality of institutions (e.g. Amin and Thrift, 1994; Audretsch & Feldman, 1996; Bronzini & Piselli, 2009; Buesa et al., 2010; Cantwell & Iammarino, 2000; Furman et al., 2002; Hagedoorn, 2002; Rodríguez-Pose & Crescenzi, 2008). Recent literature investigating these factors in European NUTS2 regions, although lacking of proper sectoral breakdown, has shown that knowledge outcomes are explained by the different elements underpinning their innovation systems: their (National and Regional) economic environment, the innovation capacity of their industrial structure, the university potentiality as well as their expenditures in R&D (e.g. Buesa et al. 2010).

Although regions are embedded in national innovation systems (Freeman, 1987; Lundvall, 1992 and Nelson, 1993) they have very peculiar propensity to develop knowledge because many factors have after all a local character (as the analysis performed until now seems also to suggest). This local character depends on local institutional and governance settings, but also on the specificity of regional labour market; on the attitude to knowledge collaborations, often driven by ad hoc regional policies; and on contextual educational and R&D institutions, professional tradition, and experiences (Hotz-Hart, 2003; Asheim & Coenen, 2005; Asheim & Gentler 2005). Therefore, differences in the attitude of regions in knowledge creation are mainly due to the specific setting of regional organizations and institutions (Cooke, 2005; Asheim & Coenen, 2005). This implies that in Europe - considering the heterogeneity that exists among regions - national factors are surely important but not enough for grasping what can sustain less performing regions in their R&I performances.

To investigate the relation between determinants and knowledge creation in EU regions we apply a linear regression model (Ordinary Least Square). In order to disentangle better the regional from the national influences the first step it is then to include in the analysis only variables at regional level, and only in the second step to include one variable that controls also for national effect and in particular if the region belong to Widening or No Widening countries. As outcome variables for the analysis related to publications we use the number of Health publications in fractional terms present in Scopus specifically assigned to the Health thematic priority; for patents we use instead the number of EPO patents applications by region of inventor related to the same thematic priority¹¹. As determinants we use a large set of contextual and sectoral indicators which cover different parts of

¹¹ We excluded from the analysis those regions without any publications or patents activities in Health.

the RegHealth-RI blocks. Those indicators include R&D expenditure expressed in percentage of GDP, quality of human resources expressed in terms of knowledge workers¹², available infrastructures (proxies with recent medical schools data), variables of knowledge flows and networking (proxies with Health priority co-patenting activities with global partners, participation in Health priority FP7 projects as well as the presence of firms in those projects). We control also for the quality of the industrial structure (proxies with the participation in clusters in advanced health sectors¹³).

Since literature stresses that the quality of a regional innovation system is crucial for determining the propensity of R&I in the region we look also at some proxies related to give indications about the quality of institutions. We use 1) the effectiveness of government and 2) the typology of regions developed in the ESPON – KIT project¹⁴, on the basis of the technological specialization (low tech region, advanced service, advanced manufacturing region or high tech region). We control then for the presence of on-going clinical trials that may serve the creation of new knowledge in the sector and that maybe related directly and indirectly to the development of patents/publications in Health. For the two different outcomes patents and publications, we checked also the experience of the region in patenting when investigating the publications propensity and in publication when investigating the patents propensity. Other important external conditions that we consider in the analysis are then the degree of specialization of the region in the Health sector (HI index) and the size of the region (expressed here in terms of population and in terms of potential market).

In order to consider better the magnitude of the values when there is a great variation in the distribution, the outcomes indicators (publications and patents) as other variables related to knowledge are expressed in logarithmic term.

It is important to notice that for ensuring the maximum coverage¹⁵ of EU regions at NUTS2 level and the validity of the model in terms of multicollinearity, heteroscedasticity and normality some variables used in the correlation matrix such as GDP or the variable related to human resources in science and technology could not be included in this regression analysis. Moreover it was not possible to disentangle the different R&D expenditures in terms of HERD, BERD and GOVERD. Table 7 presents the results of the analysis¹⁶.

As it is possible to observe beyond the size and the specialization of the region in the Health sector, one of the main determinants of knowledge creation in terms of publications propensity remains the regional R&D expenditure in relation to the specific GDP. Surprisingly having a high number of Health schools is not significant probably because what really count in the Health sector is the quality of the

¹² Knowledge workers are, in the ILO definition, “persons whose education and high level of technical expertise qualify them for employment in knowledge-based industries”. Such a variable has been used here because of good quality of data of this indicator but also because it can be considered a good proxy of the ability of human resources to create and use knowledge throughout the regional economy since it refers to the professional profiles of the knowledge workers more than the knowledge workers per se.

¹³ It is very difficult to provide an overall map of all EU clusters in the Health sector or in life science because there are different interpretation of what is Health or Life Science in different EU regions. For this reason we preferred to give a flag to the regions that have been considered by the EU cluster observatory the top performing regions in two of the ten identified emerging industries and that are specifically related to Health: biopharmaceutical and medical devices (European Cluster panorama, 2014).

¹⁴ https://www.espon.eu/main/Menu_Projects/Menu_AppliedResearch/kit.html

¹⁵ While for some variables such as publications, on-going clinical trials or medical schools data are available for all EU regions, for other variables the missing values reduced the sample to 205 regions. In total the missing observations are few compared to the average of quantitative studies at regional level (Buesa et al. 2010) and our sample guaranties at least the coverage of regions for all EU countries but Croatia.

¹⁶ We have excluded from the analysis the regions related to France's overseas as well as the Spanish Ceuta and Melilla while included the mono-regions NUTS00 Cyprus, Estonia, Lithuania, Luxemburg, Latvia, and Malta.

institutes where to conduct the research more than the number of schools in which the Health is taught. Having a general pool in the region of knowledge workers is also not significant, but in this case this result may be biased because of the typology of indicator used. The results show also that regions with relatively more private actors and less universities and public actors have worst research performances. In general the model seems to indicate that the presence of some agglomeration economy as well as the presence of a certain general technological capacity of the region, particularly if dedicated to manufacturing activities, it is not relevant, if not negative. One can guess that for sustaining independent public research there should be also a certain distance from the influence of local market logics since the industry in some regions may tend to absorb and snatch resources that can otherwise be dedicated to public research activities.

What results instead positive for increasing publication propensity in the EU regions is not only having previous experience in Health knowledge creation, but also an active participation in clinical trials. This suggests that new scientific and technological advancements performed in the specific Health sector at regional level may give start to new scientific research to be conducted. The analysis also shows that good performances in publications can be found in regions belonging to Widening countries or that are considered peripheral (so been a region in a Widening country does not penalize so much the production of science in this sector). This is not surprising since codified knowledge, as it can be a large part of knowledge contained in scientific publications, is usually less linked to the territorial aspects (Polanyi, 1983). This is also confirmed by the fact that for increasing publications performances what seems to count is the participation in international projects in which it is possible to exchange knowledge with other partners involved in research activities.

If we compare the determinants of publications propensity with the determinants of patents propensity we observe that besides R&D expenditure, the size of the region as well as the specialization in this sector, there are other determinants of these two knowledge creation outcomes which may deserve some attention.

Tab 5¹⁷ (contrary to what happen for publications) shows that there is a stronger propensity to patents in regions where it exists already some related agglomeration economy and good institutions. The higher propensity is also related to regions with a high tech industrial structure or that have actors capable of maintaining international cooperation of technological nature with global players. It is therefore not a surprise that this second analysis shows that a higher propensity to patent remain after all a prerogative of Non-Widening countries.

To summarize the overall analysis indicates that although R&D expenditure may be an important discriminant for knowledge creation, patenting in this sector remains mainly a well performed activity concentrated in regions belonging to No Widening countries. Regions that have already technological and industry capacity and where it is possible to find favoring institutions. Publications activities seems instead less context specific, therefore good performances can be sustained also in more peripheral regions increasing, for example, their capacity to participate in international research projects or sustaining the quality (more than the number) of the scientific research conducted locally.

¹⁷ In analysis of patenting propensity we could include also Cantabria region (ES13), thus leading to the presence of 206 observations instead of 205 as in the publication propensity estimation.

Table 7 - Determinants of Health publications propensity for EU regions

	All regional effects	National effect
Experience in Health Patents	0.198*** [0.054]	0.187*** [0.057]
On-going clinical trials	0.277*** [0.057]	0.285*** [0.059]
R&D expenditure on GDP	0.131*** [0.041]	0.128*** [0.040]
Knowledge workers	0.012 [0.010]	0.015 [0.011]
Medical schools	0.026 [0.033]	0.026 [0.033]
International knowledge flow	-0.018 [0.042]	-0.018 [0.042]
FP7 project participation	0.003*** [0.001]	0.003*** [0.001]
EFPIA participation in FP7 projects	-0.007** [0.003]	-0.007** [0.003]
Firms participation in FP7 projects	-0.012*** [0.002]	-0.012*** [0.002]
Biopharmaceutical cluster	-0.052 [0.100]	-0.048 [0.100]
Medical Devices cluster	-0.070 [0.095]	-0.070 [0.095]
Government effectiveness	-0.090 [0.054]	-0.102* [0.054]
Potential market size	-0.000* [0.000]	-0.000* [0.000]
Advanced service region	-0.119 [0.158]	-0.133 [0.161]
Advanced manufacturing region	-0.404*** [0.154]	-0.394*** [0.150]
Technologically advanced region	-0.148 [0.167]	-0.162 [0.170]
Population	0.015*** [0.004]	0.015*** [0.004]
Health Specialization Index	0.780*** [0.161]	0.755*** [0.154]
Widening effect		-0.101 [0.148]
Constant	2.849*** [0.418]	2.797*** [0.447]
N	205	205
ll	-148.350	-148.045
R-squared	0.8100	0.8105
P	0	0

Table 8 - Determinants of Health patents propensity for EU regions

Linear regression (OLS)	All regional effects	National effect
Experience in Health Publications (frac)	0.234*	0.188
	[0.125]	[0.124]
On-going clinical trials	-0.032	0.011
	[0.085]	[0.089]
R&D expenditure on GDP	0.242***	0.218***
	[0.063]	[0.061]
Knowledge workers	0.014	0.028*
	[0.016]	[0.017]
Medical schools	-0.061	-0.058
	[0.039]	[0.037]
International knowledge flow	0.438***	0.415***
	[0.071]	[0.068]
FP7 project participation	0.002	0.002*
	[0.001]	[0.001]
EFPIA participation in FP7 projects	-0.001	-0.001
	[0.006]	[0.006]
Firms participation in FP7 projects	0.009***	0.008**
	[0.003]	[0.003]
Biopharmaceutical cluster	0.379***	0.375***
	[0.144]	[0.140]
Medical Devices cluster	0.677***	0.652***
	[0.181]	[0.181]
Government effectiveness	0.281***	0.207**
	[0.091]	[0.100]
Potential market size	0.000	0.000
	[0.000]	[0.000]
Advanced service region	0.241	0.160
	[0.246]	[0.256]
Advanced manufacturing region	0.404	0.422
	[0.281]	[0.270]
Technologically advanced region	0.509**	0.421
	[0.251]	[0.262]
Population	0.030***	0.029***
	[0.006]	[0.006]
Health Specialization Index	0.491**	0.375*
	[0.224]	[0.215]
Widening effect		-0.492**
		[0.224]
Constant	-2.356***	-2.397***
	[0.623]	[0.638]
N	206	206
ll	-254.03	-251.162
R-squared	0.7032	0.7114
P	0	0

3.3. A proposal for a Composite Indicator of Health Research Excellence

Over the last years, scholars have developed several indicators to measure in a synthetic way the outcomes of the R&I process, as well as its excellence across countries and regions. If the Innovation Union Scoreboard and the Regional Innovation Scoreboard – as mentioned in the previous sections – aim at assessing the innovativeness level of EU countries and regions, they focus only partially on research outcomes. Therefore, within the EC it has been developed a different indicator focused particularly on scientific research. We refer to the composite indicator on Research Excellence, put forward in an EC-JRC report (2013).

This indicator aims at measuring research excellence in Europe, at country level, from a multiple point of view. In fact, the (top) quality of scientific and technological outputs derives from four different typologies of research activities: publications; patents; quality of universities and research institutes; and capacity to receive prestigious grants such as the ERC ones.

More in details, the four components of the indicator are:

1. A field-normalised number of highly cited publications of a country as measured by the top 10 % most cited publications (in all disciplines) per total number of publications.
2. The number of high quality patent applications of a country as measured by the number of patents filed under the Patent Cooperation Treaty (PCT) per million inhabitants.
3. The number of world class universities and research institutes in a country as measured by the number of organisations of a country in the top 250 universities and 50 research institutes divided by gross expenditures in R&D of a country.
4. The number of high prestige research grants received by a country as measured by the total value of European Research Council grants received divided by public R&D expenditures of a country.

This indicator has not only an intrinsic motivation, which is to quantify altogether the different dimensions of research excellence. From a policy perspective, the indicator provides a synthetic overview of R&I to better understand which European countries are less performing and therefore in need of specific policy support. Not by chance, the Widening vs. Non-Widening distinction – that we have also used throughout this report – derives from the Research Excellence indicator's level.

Dealing with Health R&I outcomes, the RegHealth-RI project has faced the need to calculate an indicator similar to the EC-JRC one. However, as anticipated in the methodological section, the “double” adaptation – regionalisation and sectorialisation – has not been feasible. It has been possible to recreate a similar indicator for Health in the EU-28 countries, with minor adaptations that we discuss hereafter. Instead, the regionalisation of this indicator for the Health sector – that we consider very important for policy support reasons – is still not measurable for strong lack of data (to make an example, the lack of information of most cited publications available for all regions). Moreover, given the problematic issues identified also at the national level (see the rest of this section below) for some variables, the risk of calculating a regional indicator was to increase even more its unreliability. At the national level, we have calculated the composite indicator for Health Research Excellence, using a similar methodology to the one in the EC-JRC report. As in that case, we have normalized all the variables into a scale from 10 to 100 using the min-max method and then aggregated together those variables using the geometric average. Moreover, as for the JRC report the variable related to ERC has been transformed using the natural logarithm.

The main difference between the EC-JRC indicator and our Health one derives from:

- Differences in the years used for calculation;
- Lack of similar data on top Health universities and PROs.

In particular, this second issue is motivated by the existence of only a sub-set of universities and PROs used for the calculation. Having used data coming from a previous EC project, in which only a limited number of top universities and PROs were considered, we might face a bias in favour of some countries. Namely those for which the top universities and PROs considered in the previous EC project are not exactly the top ones in Health. However, given the high concentration of excellence on few institutions in each country, we are confident that this bias is very limited.

As a last minor issue, we considered the total number, and not the average, of PCT patents per population.

Table 9 below synthesises and compares the variables used in the two indicators.

Table 9 – Variables included in the composite indicators

Composite indicator research excellence 2010			
(1) Top 10% most cited publications (2000-2007)	(2) Top Universities & PROs per GERD (2003-2007, 2004-2008)	(3) PCT Patents per population (2000-2008)	(4) ERC Grants per public R&D (2007-2011)
REGHEALTH-RI composite indicator research excellence			
(1) Health Top 10% most cited Publications (2008-2009)	(2) Health TOP universities and PROs (2007-2012)	(3) PCT patents per population (2008-2010)	(4) ERC Grants per public R&D (GERD+HERD) (updated years)

The intensity of the two indicators is displayed, for all EU countries, in the maps 44 and 45. In each map, the four colours represent the quartiles of the distribution. As in all the maps of this report, the countries with the highest levels of the indicator (that is in the highest quartile) are displayed with the darkest colour.

Map 44 – EC-JRC Composite Indicator of Research Excellence (map at country level in terms of quartiles)

Map 45 – RegHealth-RI project Composite Indicator of Health Research Excellence (map at country level in terms of quartiles)

As it is possible to observe when comparing the two maps, the composite indicator of Health research excellence at country level appears similar to the general one without sectorial breakdown. Nevertheless, important differences emerge in the case of some countries, such as Italy (going up to the first quartile) and Sweden (decreasing to the second quartile). Overall, the dominance of Nordic and Central-Western EU countries is confirmed. The last quartile – in both cases – includes only Eastern European countries. Hungary performs worse in the Health indicator, as compared to the general one. While the opposite happens for Portugal.

These differences highlight also some problematic issues related to the type of *variables that do not seem to capture adequately some quality aspects*. From the analysis we conducted, the most problematic variable seems to be the one related to the number of top universities and PROs: these might not capture the real quality of the research in Health conducted in the different organizations.

As a more general comment, we can observe also that in both indicators *Widening countries are strongly underestimated using ERC data on grants*. In fact, ERC grants are almost exclusively a matter of Nordic and Western EU countries. Instead, other types of indicators might display a more balanced situation, of Southern and Eastern countries performing worse, but not completely absent. We refer, for instance, to the use of EC contributions in FP7 projects instead of the ERC grants. Or, going to another category, to the idea of merging together the “top” and the “quality” measures in a unique weighted indicator. That is, calculating a variable of: Total Highly Cited Publications by Top PROs in the country *divided by* Total Highly Cited Publications in the country. Such an indicator may probably provide a more objective picture of research quality across all EU countries.

In the graph 16, we report the exact values of the two indicators, in a comparative way, for all EU countries.

Graph 16 – Comparison of the EC-JRC and RegHealth-RI composite indicators’ values, by EU country

4. CONCLUSIONS AND POLICY RECOMMENDATIONS

4.1. Conclusions

1. From a methodological point of view, there exist few conceptual frameworks altogether including health research and innovation. This lack of a “validated” theoretical framework together with the lack of data for some important variables, especially at regional level (NUTS2), make in some cases rather difficult to obtain appropriate conclusions/recommendations.
2. Sometimes, the position of some countries/regions in rankings based on a series of variables included in the analysis points out to a certain degree of unreliability in relation to data compiled by databases and information systems. See for instance the low values of Scandinavian countries (maps 9 and 10) for Medical and Pharmacy schools; or the unexpected high values of some Eastern EU regions for Health research infrastructures (map 37).
3. Selected variables have to be interpreted with caution. It is evident that ‘more’ is not always better. For example, none region/country would benefit if R&D expenditures would amount to 50% of GDP, or if most of its population are researchers. In general, for the selected variables, the health R&I performance of the regions/countries which show low values could be enhanced by improving its present figures, but from some point onwards further improvements could lead to inefficiencies.
4. Normally, countries/regions that show to have a research excellence in all fields are also the ones that have this excellence for the health sector.
5. In general, public and private R&D expenditure and personnel explain the outcome variables: the more countries/regions invest, the more they obtain in terms of publications, patents and project success. Similarly, after all “size always matters”: Regions with larger population and/or higher GDP are often associated with good R&I outcomes.
6. New scientific knowledge is without doubts a major driver of health technology innovation. However, it would be wrong to characterize the innovation and development of health technologies as only determined by scientific discovery as it is clear that technological innovation is also affected by social, economic and cultural factors.
7. Any attempt to increase the productivity of a country/region should take into account the complex interplay between the many factors contributing to their efficiency, such as the country’s or region’s characteristics and development stages. The difficulty for identifying these complex factors does not mean that they are irrelevant. In fact, these structural effects raise important issues about the adequate focus of policy analysis.
8. The country success in FP7, with few exceptions, seems to be quite in line with the country research performances. The divide between Widening and Non-Widening in the success related to projects is more evident in ERC projects than in FP7 projects. However, looking at preliminary Horizon 2020 data (especially map 24 on success rates), the situation is apparently changing in favour of Widening countries.
9. Considering the lower efforts and level of Widening countries in terms of health research inputs (e.g. expenditure in health R&D), their performance in “relative terms” looks better than in “absolute values”, thus implying their “most efficient” use of scarce resources.
10. In general, less performing regions in health R&I are present both in Widening and Non-Widening countries. The existence of clear differences in health R&I across and within countries is a clear sign and a solid reason to reconsider the application of the *Composite Indicator* for research excellence, which eligibility conditions of Widening programme are based on, not only at country but also at region level.

4.2. Recommendations

1. It would be desirable to elaborate standardised protocols or rules for selecting, gathering, processing and presenting data at EU, national and regional level.
2. It seems necessary to use complementary methods to statistical analysis for gathering information about country/region contextual and external factors (industry sector, political conditions, educational system, etc.), for instance, by means of case studies, interviews, or surveys, among others.
3. Apart from a simple counting, publications and patents should be rated according to objective criteria. Publications can be, for instance, discriminated on the basis of the quality of journal including them, which can be peer reviewed and non-peer reviewed and, similarly, journals can be classified into four different quartiles representing a higher or lower impact. On its side, patents might be, at least, distinguished between into applications, granted and transferred.
4. Albeit *excellence* in research should be a primary goal of EU research, promoting excellence, for instance, in Horizon 2020 seems to widen the gap between leading countries/regions and less performing ones.
5. The concept of *research excellence* should be better defined, explained and delineated. Accordingly, research programmes should try to include specific topics targeted to less performing countries and regions with a twofold objective: (i) facilitate them advancing towards excellent research and, (ii) shorten the gap in health R&I.
6. Policy and decision makers should be aware of particularities and factors underlying and influencing countries/regions development and health R&I performance in order to design, adopt and implement tailor-made actions and policies taking into consideration country's/region's specific needs.
7. Exploring ways to better adapt European and national initiatives to regional specificities and strengthened research and innovation policy competencies at the regional level could help to tackle the divide between European regions in health R&I.
8. The above mentioned particularities and specificities of EU regions and countries also refer to the regulatory framework of each of them. This should be considered by EU, national and regional authorities in charge of developing and implementing health R&I policies since in many times, regional or national regulation may contradict EU policies or vice versa. This fact might hinder synergies between policies at different level or even the implementation of EU in certain EU regions or countries.

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6. LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

- BERD: Business expenditure on R&D
- EFPIA: European Federation of Pharmaceutical industries and associations
- EPO: European Patent Office
- ERC: European Research Council
- GBAORD: Government budget appropriations or outlays for research and development
- GERD: Gross domestic expenditure on R&D
- GOVERD: Government expenditure on R&D
- HERD: Higher-education expenditure on R&D
- IMI: Innovative Medicines Initiative
- PCT: Patent Cooperation Treaty
- PRO: Public Research Organization
- R&D: Research and Development
- R&I: Research and Innovation
- S3: Smart Specialisation Strategy
- SMEs: Small and Medium Enterprises
- WHO: World Health Organization
- WP: Work package

7. ANNEXES

This section includes all data used in the analysis both at national and regional level. Click on the following links to download datasets in CSV or Excel formats. Data in CSV format have been divided in two files referring to national and regional data separately. By contrast, Excel file includes national and regional data in the same file.

Data at national level in CSV format	
	http://rhing-net.eu/reghealth-ri/data/RegHealth-RI_Report_National_Data_Annex.csv
Data at regional level in CSV format	
	http://rhing-net.eu/reghealth-ri/data/RegHealth-RI_Report_Regional_Data_Annex.csv
Data at national and regional level in Excel format	
	http://rhing-net.eu/reghealth-ri/data/RegHealth-RI_Report_National_Regional_Data_Annex.xlsx